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The Host Migration Graveyard:

A feasibility study in co-op games

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Graduation Work 2023-2024

Digital Arts and Entertainment

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ABSTRACT & KEY WORDS

(ENG)

Host migration is a networking process that allows another player to take over as the game host when the original host disconnects, ensuring no loss of progress for the other players. Despite its potential to improve multiplayer stability and eliminate dedicated server costs, it is generally considered as a dead concept due to technical complexity and production cost constraints. This research explores the feasibility of implementing effective host migration strategies in online co-op games made in Unity. Various approaches were researched for performance, reliability, and cost-efficiency, offering practical solutions tailored for indie developers. Not only the feasibility of host migration, but also the scalability of such an implementation was extensively tested and analyzed. There was data analysis done on 372 raw entries, comparing the performance of server-side and client-side information synchronization post host migration, which showed promising results.

(NL)

Hostmigratie is een netwerkproces waarbij een andere speler de rol van spelhost overneemt wanneer de oorspronkelijke host de verbinding verbreekt, waardoor de andere spelers geen vooruitgang verliezen. Ondanks het potentieel om de stabiliteit van multiplayer games te verbeteren en kosten voor dedicated servers te vermijden, wordt het vaak gezien als een dood concept vanwege technische complexiteit en productiekosten. Dit onderzoek verkent de haalbaarheid van effectieve strategieën voor hostmigratie in online co-op games ontwikkeld in Unity. Verschillende benaderingen zijn onderzocht op prestaties, betrouwbaarheid en kostenefficiëntie, met als doel praktische oplossingen te bieden voor indie-ontwikkelaars. Niet enkel de haalbaarheid van hostmigratie, maar ook de schaalbaarheid van een implementatie ervan werd uitgebreid getest en geanalyseerd. Er werd een data-analyse gedaan op 372 gegevens, waar de prestatie van de server-side en client-side informatie werd vergeleken na host migration, die belovende resultaten aangetoond heeft.

PREFACE

This paper provides insight and analysis into the world of host migration, which is a fascinating concept over which many people hold strong opinions. With the uptick of online multiplayer games being developed in the last two decades, it is becoming more and more feasible for indie game developers to create their own multiplayer game. The standard approach for most larger studios are to use dedicated servers to ensure uninterrupted gameplay, but this approach is difficult financially for most indie game developers, including myself. I intend to make many small co-op experiences for the world to enjoy together, for a cheap price – I’m just a small indie developer after all, I cannot compete with content against AAA games. But, with no direct guarantee of sales or player revenue, paying for dedicated servers for the next few decades is an unrealistic choice which would lose me money, as if it’s a hole in my wallet. This sparked my interest in developing without paying for servers and letting people host their own. However, this proved to be difficult due to the lack of available resources. Personally, I’ve always strived to defy the odds, become the best and provide a net-positive influence on the world. This research could be a very valuable asset, sparking innovation in the industry through an otherwise forgotten practice. It’s time to revive the graveyard of host migration, once and for all.

I would like to express my gratitude to my coach, supervisors and partner Sara who provided guidance and support throughout this process. Special thanks to the developers and supportive community behind Mirror, especially MrGadget, whose insights contributed greatly to the technical foundation of this project.

It is my hope that this paper not only sheds light on the practicality of host migration but also inspires further research and innovation in indie multiplayer game development.

Louis Vanhove

11/01/2025

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INTRODUCTION

BACKGROUND

HISTORY

“The history of online games dates back to the early days of packet-based computer networking in the 1970s, One of the first online games was MUD1, which was created in 1978.” (“Online Game,” 2024)

Since then, there has been an uptick in online games being created and played all across the world. The technologies on which these games rely have evolved greatly, together with the capabilities of computers and servers. The power of microchips has been constantly growing for the past five decades. (*Moore’s Law Has Accurately Predicted the Progress in Transistor Counts over the Last 50 Years*, n.d.)

Figure 1: Timeline of Key Developments in Server Hardware Evolution (1981–2019).

(TechTarget, 2020)

Let’s take a closer look at how players can connect to each other over the internet.

DEDICATED SERVERS

In more recent years, many games have started using dedicated servers as they have become more affordable and more powerful, offering reliability and stability. They allow for better performance (with dedicated resources and optimized hardware), as well as security and cheat prevention, allowing a controlled server to validate player actions, making sure no clients are tampering with their data. They can also provide better latency to players, given there are enough servers around the world for players to connect to. In the case that the game uses Steam Datagram Relay (SDR), the latency can be improved even further through direct data funneling from relay to server, minimizing extra network hops from the network transport (usually UDP/TCP). (GDC 2025, 2018)

These are undeniably good features of dedicated servers, which the player-hosted (client-server) architecture can not compete with. You cannot possibly have the same sense of security/cheat prevention, reliability or stability when you are putting the responsibility of hosting servers in the hands of your players. (Is There Really Any Point to Making a Client-Server Game Authoritative?, 2011; Kroupp, 2024)

Because of these advantages of dedicated servers, client-server architecture with player-hosting is rarely done by big studios anymore. This makes sense, they have made a name for themselves and have enough funding to host servers, allowing them to give their players a better experience. However, this is a fever dream that doesn't last forever. More and more games using dedicated servers cannot keep supporting the large upkeep costs, as there are thousands of games being released every month, competing for the attention of the players. This can lead to less sales and user retention and less revenue for older games, which leaves the company to bleed money, providing servers for users who no longer make them much revenue. This is not maintainable for most studios, leading to mass server shutdowns, and unhappy users, who will even go to court (they paid for the game, you shut it down, taking away what they paid for). (McEvoy, 2024)

To put this in perspective, FIFA 22's online servers are already shut down since November 2024. WWE 2K23's online services are already shut down. These games have barely been out for a few years, and the massive studios supporting them choose to not sustain the upkeep of their games. (*Watch List – Delisted Games*, 2025)

This makes sense from a business perspective, as paying for these servers for many players to use all across the world costs a lot of money. Players have high expectations of video games and their connectivity with low latency and no downtimes, even when the game gets a sudden influx of players, which the servers cannot handle.

COMMUNITY-HOSTED SERVERS

Community-hosted servers represent a decentralized approach to servers, where individual players or groups host game servers independently, moderating and customizing the game settings as they see fit. Servers hosted by the community have been popularized by games like Minecraft, Counter-Strike, and ARK: Survival Evolved. They have fostered diverse and innovative gameplay experiences that cater to niche player interests, which have even evolved to full fledged games because it was loved by so many players. An example of this is Counter-Strike's Surf game mode, where you slide on ramps and try to preserve your momentum to parkour around the map. (*Overflow on Steam*, 2021)

There are many games around with an option for community-hosted servers, which can help preserve the game for longer, as the independent third-party hosters pay for their own servers. There's a multitude of games on Steam that allow for this and for some it's a deciding factor when buying a game. (*Steam Curator*, n.d.)

Sometimes, larger companies allow the players to have their own community-hosted servers, while existing in the server rack of the actual game (funded by the studio itself). This is not something I would suggest for small studios, as a main plus point of community hosting is that it costs you less money. (*How Do Community Servers Work?*, 2021)

For indie developers, enabling community-hosted servers can reduce operational costs, as a part of your playerbase won't be using resources from the official dedicated servers. This approach also encourages player engagement and fosters stronger community bonds, as players can create their own experiences and communities. However, third party hosting can have lower server quality, security vulnerabilities, and fragmented player bases, which may impact overall game stability and user experience.

PEER-2-PEER

Peer-to-peer (P2P) networking is a decentralized multiplayer model, which means that there is no central server that players connect to. Every player acts as both a client and a server. P2P networking is commonly used in smaller-scale or older indie multiplayer games due to its simplicity and cost-effectiveness. (*What Is Peer-to-Peer Networking for Multiplayer Games?*, n.d.)

One of the primary advantages of P2P networking is its low operational cost. Since there is no need for dedicated servers, developers don't need to spend a penny on servers. Additionally, P2P setups can offer lower latency in some cases, as data is transmitted directly between players without intermediary servers. This only holds true when players are close together physically and have high internet speed.

However, P2P networking comes with notable challenges. Security is a large concern, as exposing players' IP addresses can lead to vulnerabilities like DDOS (Distributed Denial Of Service) attacks or cheating (as each client is also acting as a server). If one player's connection drops, it can affect the entire game session, which is less than desirable. (*Understanding Peer-to-Peer Networking In Multiplayer Games*, 2024)

Because players connect directly to each other, the players need to have an ISP which allows for NAT traversal and possibly port forwarding to ensure that they can connect with each other in the first place. (Kroupp, 2024)

To mitigate these issues, hybrid models combining P2P networking with relay servers have been introduced. Relay servers act as intermediaries, managing player connections without hosting the game state, thus improving connection stability and enhancing security. This hybrid approach allows developers to balance cost-efficiency with a more secure and stable multiplayer experience. We will dive deeper into this in the next topic.

RELAY WITH CLIENT-SERVER ARCHITECTURE

A client-server model with a relay intermediary is a hybrid networking architecture where player data is routed through a relay server rather than direct client-to-client communication. In this setup, the relay server handles traffic between the host and clients, improving connection reliability and protecting player privacy. Unlike traditional dedicated servers that manage the entire game state, relay servers only forward data packets, reducing operational costs while offering many of the stability and security benefits of dedicated servers. (Relay Servers, n.d.; *What Are Relay Servers for Multiplayer Games?*, n.d.)

One major advantage of using relay servers is enhanced security. By masking IP addresses of clients, relay servers prevent direct exposure to potential DDoS attacks and other security threats. Relay networks also help resolve NAT

traversal issues, allowing players behind strict firewalls to connect smoothly. This approach combines the affordability of peer-to-peer networking with the security and reliability closer to that of dedicated servers.

However, routing data through relay servers can introduce additional latency compared to direct P2P connections. The performance impact depends on the server's location relative to the players and the efficiency of the relay infrastructure. Despite this trade-off, relay intermediaries provide a cost-effective and scalable solution for indie developers seeking to enhance multiplayer stability without investing in full-scale dedicated servers.

Figure 2: Client-Relay Server Network Architecture

This is what the architecture looks like, with the black laptops being the clients, and the central red laptop being the relay server. The relay server merely forwards the packets to the right clients. (Dongen, 2014)

PERSONAL INSPIRATION

I am a game programmer and developer, who is looking to make many small games and publish them for the world to enjoy. Since 2013 I've been inseparable from video games, starting out on my father's iPhone with Minecraft: Pocket Edition and eventually getting the Java edition on my very first laptop. I learned to speak English through Minecraft, made many friends and made lots of fun memories. It sparked a passion inside of me for multiplayer games, especially games where you can play together with friends or strangers by your side. I had quickly fallen in love with the co-operative and competitive genre, leading me to spend much of my free time online. I started playing competitively in Counter-Strike, reaching the highest rank on both normal matchmaking and Facelt (Level10). As well as being top500 in Overwatch open queue and competing in Fortnite's first seasons, being in the top 150 players in Belgium. However, playing at a high level requires time to practice, while much of my time goes to developing games nowadays. For this reason, I prefer playing co-op games with my friends from time to time, and it made me wonder if I could build such a game. There have been more and more independent game developers suddenly making co-op games that many players have loved (e.g Muck, Lethal company). I wondered if I could do the same, but quickly realized I had no budget or funding for servers. After some research, I decided to take the plunge and start learning Mirror Networking for Unity. This led me to becoming a better developer, after

which I decided to go to Unite Barcelona (2024). I decided to follow as many multiplayer talks as possible, to learn as much as possible for my future co-op games. There was a talk by Paolo Abela, a senior software engineer at Unity and online game consultant, at which I asked him whether he thought host migration was a necessity for good user experience. I had previously always heard it was a dead concept with no future which I shouldn't bother with, but he shared his thoughts, detailing how it was important and I was fascinated. I went home and looked for research on it, but there was nothing official to be found, just a few example repositories and proprietary solutions from big companies. I finally had the chance to make a difference in this industry, however small it was.

PURPOSE OF THE RESEARCH

The primary aim of this research is to evaluate the feasibility of implementing effective host migration strategies in online multiplayer co-op games developed with Unity. This study focuses on identifying and comparing various host migration approaches based on performance, reliability, and cost-efficiency. The goal is to provide practical, scalable solutions that indie developers can adopt to enhance player retention and game stability without incurring the high costs of dedicated servers.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

As the purpose of this research is to evaluate the feasibility of host migration and trying to find an efficient solution that is scalable and easily adaptable for developers, these research questions help us learn more and drive us towards a solid solution.

RESEARCH QUESTION 1: CONTEXT FEASIBILITY

In which contexts is host migration a feasible solution in game development for online multiplayer co-op games?

RESEARCH QUESTION 2: MIGRATION STRATEGIES

What are the most effective strategies for implementing host migration in a player-hosted (client-server) architecture for online multiplayer co-op games for indie studios using Unity?

HYPOTHESES

RESEARCH QUESTION 1: CONTEXT FEASIBILITY

I suspect that the only contexts this will be a viable solution for is in co-op games where cheating does not matter at all, so there shouldn't be leaderboard mechanics or other initiatives inviting ultra-competitive play. I believe that if there are mechanics like this in place and you keep getting beat by blatant cheaters, it would really hurt player experience. When the host disconnects and the new host fills that role, I presume the data of the lobby could be manipulated to skip waves, kill other players, teleport to unreachable locations, skip to the end of the game instantly, etc.

I also hypothesize that the scope of the game cannot be too large as a lot of data syncing might take a long time and not be synced properly. Games with lots of content like Real Time Strategy Games (RTS) would probably be a bad fit.

RESEARCH QUESTION 2: MIGRATION STRATEGIES

I carefully considered my options when starting out as there are many solutions possible. The existing resources online do not cover strategies, but just showcases their proprietary code in action or with a GitHub repository linked, in which it is a quick proof of concept with the main goal of just working. The most promising resource is the official Mirror FAQ in the documentation and the official Unity UNET documentation, but it does not go into depth on strategy. Hence, I made my own strategies to consider further and possibly try out. (FAQ | Mirror, 2021; Unity - Manual: Host Migration, n.d.)

Hypothesis 1: Designating the backup host

There are two main options here: either I designate one host, or an ordered list of hosts (both options synchronized to all clients, so they know who to reconnect to). (FAQ | Mirror, 2021)

I suspect that designating an ordered list of new hosts when starting the game (that just started, not the lobby) synced across clients may provide more stability. When the host disconnects, the clients reconnect to the next host in line. The client which will become the host knows about this as the list is ordered and synced. I predict this approach would work best, as there's no unnecessary bandwidth usage - but this only works if the new host manages to save the information to reconstruct the scene. This might prove difficult as when the host disconnects, the connection to the server cuts off. This uncertainty is hard to answer without actively testing it out, we will see in the future if this is possible or not. If this does prove to be possible, having just one backup host that keeps being reassigned will work.

Hypothesis 2: Interval state synchronization

I believe that implementing regular state synchronization with a secondary client will maintain game state consistency during host migration. This could be done with a tick rate system, sending over all necessary information to the players to reconstruct the scene. This data has to be persistent though, so it does not get lost when the host leaves. I predict this approach will be the easiest and cheapest to implement if we're sending the entire save, but this will affect latency tremendously and there might be a short pause while data gets deserialized and the scene gets reloaded. Some data might be lost between intervals, depending on how short the ticks are. Sending over entire saves will hardly be possible, as that would likely lag out the game every few ticks – it will have to be incremental updates that are sent only. Even then, in the best case scenario, you cannot guarantee all data being synced (losing a few seconds of progress each time).

Hypothesis 3: Co-host synchronization

Designating a co-host when the game starts, which acts like a fail-safe for the game. This co-host is chosen when the game starts (not the lobby, the actual game) by best ping, and is sent all of the information the server receives. This would double the network traffic for this user, but ensure that no data is lost at all, which leads me to believe this will be better than the interval synchronization method, would this happen to work.

Hypothesis 4: Relay intermediary (free)

For indie studios running their online multiplayer game on Steam, the transport can be sent through a Steam relay. This makes it so that data is networked with Steam as a middleman, simply passing through the data to other clients, allowing for a seamless, free host migration. This procedure could be done with any free relay service.

This hypothesis was written before I learned about NAT traversal and port forwarding limitations, which made this a necessary step for the host migration to work, in retrospect.

Hypothesis 5: Dedicated server backup (paid fallback case)

If all of the previous approaches fall through, using a dedicated server or a cloud-based relay which re-routes the network to some listen server might be the only way to solve this. This would be paid, which would not be great for indie studios, but if it's the only possible way, it's still a step in the right direction. It would cost less than hosting dedicated-servers and provide a better user experience. This is the way Photon (PUN2) used to handle it behind the scenes, so it is definitely possible - but dedicated servers cost money and this might not be the best option for indie studios. (*Fusion 2 Host Migration API | Photon Engine, n.d.*)

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

PLAYER EXPERIENCE:

The most important reason to consider host migration is to ensure that your players have a good experience playing your game; you could make the most fun game possible, but if all of the players lose their rewards because the host leaves the game, that's an issue. Such an experience is inevitable when you make a game where your players host their own lobbies, and function as the server, without host migration implemented. No matter how well you design your game around this, people's internet will cut out, computers will crash, or sometimes the host will just want to stop playing the game; he's not obligated to be there.

This begs the question: Is it actually important? Do players really care about this?

Some examples of negative reviews, publicly posted on the Steam page of *Liar's bar*, a game about bluffing released in October 2024, made with Mirror, using player-hosted (client-server) architecture without host migration. (*Liar's Bar on Steam, n.d.*)

Figure 3: User Feedback Illustrating a need for host migration in Multiplayer Games

This is of course just an extract from the page, the overwhelming majority of the reviews are positive, but most of the negative reviews revolve around cheating or the host leaving. Cheating is something we'll discuss later (what niches is this architecture viable). I believe the developer could have benefitted from using dedicated servers.

For the host migration, you can see many players in the reviews so upset about the host leaving, that even though they've played this small game for many hours, it bothers them enough to write a negative review. Again, this can be attributed to the game design (player dies and has to wait for the game to finish) – but this is something that could have been prevented with host migration.

NETWORKING:

There are quite a few topics to cover over networking; host migration is simple on paper but not an easy concept under the hood, it takes quite a lot of effort, time and knowledge to create. This paper will briefly discuss foundational networking concepts relevant to host migration but is not intended as a comprehensive guide to game networking. For a more in-depth exploration, I highly recommend the book *“Building Multiplayer Games in Unity using Mirror Networking”* by Dylan Engelbrecht, which offers a detailed explanation of networking topics for developers with limited background knowledge.

PACKETS

In networking, data is broken down into small units called packets for transmission over the internet. Each packet contains a portion of the data along with headers that specify its source, destination, and sequence order. This data is not a part of the payload that you actually send, but an addition to double-check on retrieval if everything arrived correctly. Multiplayer games rely heavily on packet-based communication to synchronize game state across players. Packet loss or delays can lead to lag, desynchronization, or gameplay disruptions. This is an example of a TCP packet, the green section is what you actually send (max 64KB per packet). (Maximum Packet Size for a TCP Connection | Baeldung on Computer Science, n.d.; Networking Fundamentals, 2024)

Figure 4: Structure of UDP and TCP Packets

(Dylan Engelbrecht, 2021)

PORTS

In computer networking, ports are virtual communication endpoints that allow multiple services or applications to coexist on a single device by differentiating network traffic. Each port is identified by a unique number ranging from 0 to 65535, as defined by the Internet Assigned Numbers Authority (IANA). These port numbers are categorized into three ranges, depending on their utility, but this is not something you have to worry about in this paper.

In multiplayer gaming, depending on how the game is architected, specific ports must be open to facilitate smooth connectivity between players and servers. For instance, Minecraft servers typically use port 25565

Proper port management ensures that data packets reach the correct application, enabling seamless gameplay experiences. Understanding and configuring ports appropriately is crucial for network security and performance, as open ports can be potential entry points for unauthorized access if not properly managed. Don't expect your players to be able to do this properly, they are likely not network engineers. ("Port (Computer Networking)," 2025)

PORT FORWARDING

Port forwarding enables you to host multiplayer game servers on your computer. It does so by opening a passage in the firewall for connections targeting a specific game. This allows outside players to connect to your device without being previously digitally invited to do so.

You need port forwarding to host servers for multiplayer games over the internet. (Klimas, 2023)

IP ADDRESS

An IP address is a unique numerical label assigned to each device connected to a computer network that uses the Internet Protocol for communication. (*Understanding the Network Layer and IP*, 2024)

In order for IP packets to know where they came from, and where they're going, each device connected to the network requires a unique IPv4 address. This IPv4 address is a 32-bit integer value, most often represented in dot-decimal notation.

This structure consists of four binary octets of the address, which looks like this:

10010011.10011101.11010101.01110100

However, because they're represented individually in decimal numbers, those binary octets look more like the following to the user:

147.157.213.116

The preceding number is a typical representation of an IPv4 address. Since each piece of an IPv4 address is represented by an 8-bit octet, our minimum decimal value is 0, and the maximum value is 255.

IPV4

IPv4 (Internet Protocol version 4) is the fourth version of the Internet Protocol, utilizing a 32-bit address scheme allowing for approximately 4.3 billion unique addresses. Due to the limited number of addresses, IPv4 is being supplemented by IPv6, which offers a vastly larger address space. (*Understanding the Network Layer and IP*, 2024)

IPV6

IPv6 provides a 128-bit address, significantly larger than IPv4's 32-bit address. However, IPv6 adoption has been slow due to certain drawbacks:

- Not backward compatible: IPv4 devices cannot communicate with IPv6 networks.
- High cost: ISPs require significant hardware upgrades to support IPv6.

IPv6 addresses are in the format X.X.X.X.X.X.X, where each X is a 16-bit hexadecimal number. (*Understanding the Network Layer and IP*, 2024)

NAT

Network Address Translation (NAT) is a method used by routers to translate private (not globally unique) IP addresses into a single public IP address. This allows multiple devices on a local network to access external networks, like the internet, using one public IP address. NAT helps conserve the limited number of IPv4 addresses and adds a layer of security by hiding internal IP addresses. (*Network Address Translation (NAT)*, 2024)

NAT helps us with two things. It helps alleviate the global IPv4 address exhaustion crisis and it allows devices on private networks to connect to publicly hosted content, in our case – game servers. But what happens if we'd like

our customers to be able to host their own game servers? The answer lies in an extension of NAT, called port forwarding. Typically, NAT uses a one-to-many translation, mapping multiple private IP addresses to a single public IP address. This is common in configurations such as your home network, even your office network.

(Dylan Engelbrecht, Building ...)

TCP VS UDP

Transmission Control Protocol (TCP) and User Datagram Protocol (UDP) are core protocols of the Internet Protocol Suite. TCP provides reliable, ordered, and error-checked delivery of data between applications, making it suitable for applications where data integrity is crucial. However, this reliability introduces latency. In contrast, UDP offers a connectionless datagram service that emphasizes reduced latency over reliability, making it ideal for time-sensitive applications like online gaming and live broadcasts. (*What Is TCP/IP?*, 2024)

“TCP is reliable out of the box but carries more network overhead. UDP is connectionless and unreliable in a network context. However, there are ways to get reliability out of UDP.” (Dylan Engelbrecht, 2021)

KCP

KCP is a fast and reliable protocol built on top of UDP. It enhances UDP by implementing features like error correction and congestion control, providing a balance between speed and reliability.

- 100% C#.
- Works on all platforms except WebGL.
- Heavy test coverage (83.5%).
- Extremely fast.
- Extremely simple.

KCP is a fast and reliable protocol that can achieve the transmission effect of a reduction of the average latency by 30% to 40% and reduction of the maximum delay threefold, at the cost of 10% to 20% more bandwidth used than TCP. (*KCP - A Fast and Reliable ARQ Protocol*, 2024)

The mirror team is excited about KCP transport and highly recommend trying it in your project.

Previously, they had pure C# transports that were slow, and native C transports that were fast, but hard to maintain. KCP brings us the best of both worlds: it's as fast as the native C transports, while still being easy to maintain because it's 100% pure C#! (*KCP Transport | Mirror*, 2022)

STEAM DATAGRAM RELAY

Valve's Steam Datagram Relay (SDR) is a virtual private gaming network that routes game traffic through Valve's infrastructure, enhancing security and performance. By relaying traffic, SDR masks players' IP addresses, protecting them from potential attacks (e.g. DOS attacks). This system supports both peer-to-peer and dedicated server

architectures, facilitating flexible multiplayer implementations. (*Steam Datagram Relay (Steamworks Documentation)*, n.d.)

FIZZYSTEAMWORKS

FizzySteamworks is a community-maintained transport for the Mirror networking framework in Unity, utilizing Steam's networking capabilities to facilitate peer-to-peer (P2P) connections. It leverages Steamworks.NET, a C# wrapper for the Steamworks API, to integrate Steam's P2P networking into Unity projects.

By incorporating FizzySteamworks, we can utilize Steam's networking features, including NAT traversal and relay servers, to enhance connectivity in multiplayer games. (FizzySteamworks Transport | Mirror, 2021; Hoffmann, 2019/2025)

ISP:

An Internet Service Provider (ISP) is a company that offers individuals and organizations access to the internet and related services. ISPs utilize various technologies—such as dial-up, DSL, cable, fiber-optic, and satellite connections—to deliver internet connectivity to their customers. They play a crucial role in maintaining the infrastructure that facilitates internet access, including managing network equipment and ensuring data transmission reliability. (*Internet Service Provider (ISP)*, 2024)

“It’s important to mention that not all routers support port forwarding, especially in the case of ISP-provided routers with custom configurations. Some ISP networks do not support port forwarding.” (Dylan Engelbrecht, 2021)

DEDICATED SERVERS:

A dedicated server is a remote server exclusively allocated to an individual, organization, or application, such as a website or game. Unlike shared hosting, dedicated servers provide full control over server resources, ensuring optimal performance, security, and customization. In gaming, dedicated servers host multiplayer environments, offering stability and reducing latency for players. (Mildenberger, 2024)

Developing for dedicated servers will require you to make separate builds for server and client, with the server build being an extremely stripped down version running the logic (this is done to preserve resources and thus money). To avoid licensing costs for servers, it’s advised to run Linux as its operating system. Build automation is highly recommended to speed up this procedure.

VPS SERVERS:

A VPS server, or Virtual Private Server, is essentially a slice of a dedicated server shared by several users. VPS servers run virtual machines on a dedicated server. One dedicated server (depending on its performance) could be sectioned off into four VPS servers. Four users can use the same hardware for different purposes, but they can only harness 25% of the server hardware’s total capability.

This is not a great idea for official games servers, especially if you intend to build a big community: these servers don't have the adequate power compared to dedicated servers, and if the other clients on your VPS get a DDOS (distributed denial of service) attack, your game servers will go down too.

This is a path you can go down, but I do not recommend it and will not be diving deeper into this. (Tuwiner, 2024)

ORCHESTRATION:

Game server orchestration is the ongoing process of adapting the availability of game servers against player demand to make sure your game runs smoothly. Although this is really important, in case your game blows up, ideally players will never even be aware it's happening. Effective orchestration is invisible. (*Seven Things You Need to Know about Game Server Hosting Orchestration for a Great Player Experience*, 2021)

PEER-2-PEER:

In a Peer-to-Peer (P2P) network, each participant, or "peer," functions simultaneously as both a client and a server. This decentralized architecture allows for direct resource sharing among nodes without the need for a central server. P2P networks are commonly used in file-sharing applications and certain gaming scenarios but may face challenges related to security and performance. (*Peer-to-Peer (P2P) Architecture*, 2024)

CLIENT-SERVER ARCHITECTURE:

Client-server architecture is a cornerstone of modern system design, where the network infrastructure is structured to include multiple clients and a central server. In this model, clients are devices or programs that make requests for services or resources, while the server is a powerful machine or software that fulfills these requests. (*Client-Server Architecture - System Design*, 2024)

Client/server gaming architecture refers to a typical distributed architecture for the support of networked games. In this architecture, a single node plays the role of the server, i.e., it maintains the game state and communicates with all other nodes (the clients). The server notifies game moves generated by players and computes the game state updates. (Ferretti & D'Angelo, 2018)

NETWORKING OPTIONS IN UNITY

There are many networking options available in Unity (Photon, NGO, UNET, Fishnet, Mirror)

PHOTON

Photon is a widely-used networking framework that provides real-time multiplayer capabilities for Unity applications. It offers various products, including Photon PUN (Photon Unity Networking) and Photon Fusion, catering to different networking needs. Photon services are known for their scalability, cross-platform support, and comprehensive feature set, making them suitable for a range of multiplayer game types. (Multiplayer Game Development Made Easy | Photon Engine, n.d.; Photon Fusion Pricing, n.d.; Photon Realtime Pricing, n.d.; Unity Realtime Multiplayer, Part 8, 2023)

Pricing quickly ramps up to hundreds of dollars per month, if your game becomes successful.

NETCODE FOR GAMEOBJECTS (NGO)

Developed by Unity, Netcode for GameObjects (NGO) is Unity's official networking solution designed to integrate seamlessly with the Unity ecosystem. It provides a framework for building both small-scale cooperative games and larger competitive titles. NGO offers features such as network variables, remote procedure calls (RPCs), and scene management, aiming to simplify the development of networked games within Unity. (*Unity Networking Feature Comparison Matrix - CodeSmile, 2023*)

UNET

UNet was Unity's legacy networking solution, now deprecated and replaced by more modern alternatives like NGO. While some older projects may still utilize UNet, it is no longer recommended for new developments due to its discontinuation and lack of support. (*Long List of Networking Solutions for Unity - Unity Engine, 2022*)

FISHNET: NETWORKING EVOLVED

Fish-Networking is a free open source, easy to use, feature rich HLAPI networking library for Unity. Our product is created and led by a professional game developer, and improved regularly through community feedback and submissions. (*FishNet, 2024*)

MIRROR NETWORKING:

Mirror is a high-level networking library for Unity, designed as a replacement for UNet. It focuses on simplicity and ease of use, providing a straightforward API for developers. Mirror supports various transports and is suitable for a wide range of multiplayer game types, from small co-op games to large-scale MMOs. (*Unity Networking Feature Comparison Matrix - CodeSmile, 2023*)

Originally based on UNET: battle tested since 2014 for 9 years and counting! Mirror is stable, modular & easy to use for all types of games, even small MMORPGs. The Server & Client are ONE project in order to achieve maximum productivity. (*Mirror | Network | Unity Asset Store, 2021*)

There are many popular games being created with Mirror, the latest hit being Liar's Bar. (*MirrorNetworking/Mirror, 2018/2025*)

MIRROR-RELATED TERMINOLOGY:

Mirror is the networking solution I've chosen, because it's easy to set up and integrate with Steam, and has a fantastic community which will help you out when you're stuck. It has a proven track record, with a team of friendly developers who assisted me where possible. The framework is built on top of UNET, which was made by Unity, but discontinued. They picked up the pieces and improved it a lot (UNET: 70 CCU (Concurrent users) → Mirror: 500CCU) (*A Brief History of Mirror | Mirror, 2023*)

AUTHORITY

Servers and clients can both manage a game object's behavior. The concept of "authority" refers to how and where a game object is managed. Mirror is based around "server authority" as the default state, where the Server has authority over all game objects. Player game objects are a special case and treated as having "local authority".

For this paper, we will not pay attention to authority - this is important when cheating should be prohibited. As host migration automatically enables cheating (if the user knows how to), this is not relevant. (*General / Mirror*, 2024)

COMMANDS

Commands are sent from player objects on the client to player objects on the server. For security, Commands can only be sent from YOUR player object by default, so you cannot control the objects of other players. You can bypass the authority check using `[Command(requiresAuthority = false)]`.

To make a function into a command, add the `[Command]` custom attribute to it, and optionally add the “Cmd” prefix for naming convention. This function will now be run on the server when it is called on the client. Any parameters of allowed data type will be automatically passed to the server with the command.

Commands functions should have the prefix “Cmd” and cannot be static. This is a hint when reading code that calls the command - this function is special and is not invoked locally like a normal function.

Example:

Let's say we have a networked object with a script called Enemy:

```
public class Enemy : NetworkBehaviour
{
    [SyncVar]
    public int health = 100;

    void OnMouseUp()
    {
        NetworkIdentity ni = NetworkClient.connection.identity;
        PlayerController pc = ni.GetComponent<PlayerController>();
        pc.currentTarget = gameObject;
    }
}
```

The `PlayerController` might look like this:

```
public class PlayerController : NetworkBehaviour
{
    public GameObject currentTarget;

    void Update()
    {
        if (isLocalPlayer)
            if (currentTarget != null && currentTarget.tag == "Enemy")
                if (Input.GetKeyDown(KeyCode.X))
                    CmdShoot(currentTarget);
    }

    [Command]
    public void CmdShoot(GameObject enemy)
    {
        // Do your own shot validation here because this runs on the server
        enemy.GetComponent<Enemy>().health -= 5;
    }
}
```

In this example, when a Player clicks on an Enemy, the networked enemy game object is assigned to `PlayerController.currentTarget`. When the player presses X, with a correct target selected, that target is passed through a Command, which runs on the server, to decrement the `health` SyncVar. All clients will be updated with that new value. You can then have a UI on the enemy to show the current value.

Figure 5: Example of Networked Player-Enemy Interaction Using Commands in Unity Mirror

(Remote Actions | Mirror, 2023)

Vanhove Louis

RPCs (Remote procedure calls) are a way for server game objects to make things happen on client game objects.

There are two types of RPCs available: ClientRPC (goes to all clients) and TargetRPC (goes to the target you want)

Client RPC calls are not restricted to player game objects, and may be called on any game object with a Network Identity component.

To define a Client RPC call in your code, you must decorate the method with `[ClientRpc]`. While not required, it is strongly suggested to prefix method names with `Rpc` so it's easier to recognize in your calling code what will be happening. (*Network Behaviour | Mirror, 2023*)

TargetRPC:

TargetRpc functions are called by user code on the server, and then invoked on the corresponding client object on the client of the specified NetworkConnection. The arguments to the RPC call are serialized across the network, so that the client function is invoked with the same values as the function on the server. These functions should begin with the prefix "Target" for naming convention and cannot be static.

Context Matters:

If the first parameter of your TargetRpc method is a NetworkConnection then that's the connection that will receive the message regardless of context.

If the first parameter is any other type, then the owner client of the object with the script containing your TargetRpc will receive the message. (*Remote Actions | Mirror, 2023*)

This example shows how a client can use a Command to make a request to the server (`CmdMagic`) by including another Player's `connectionToClient` as one of the parameters of the `TargetRpc` invoked directly from that Command:

```
public class Player : NetworkBehaviour
{
    public int health;

    [Command]
    void CmdMagic(GameObject target, int damage)
    {
        target.GetComponent<Player>().health -= damage;

        NetworkIdentity opponentIdentity = target.GetComponent<NetworkIdentity>();
        TargetDoMagic(opponentIdentity.connectionToClient, damage);
    }

    [TargetRpc]
    public void TargetDoMagic(NetworkConnectionToClient target, int damage)
    {
        // This will appear on the opponent's client, not the attacking player's
        Debug.Log($"Magic Damage = {damage}");
    }

    // Heal thyself
    [Command]
    public void CmdHealMe()
    {
        health += 10;
        TargetHealed(10);
    }

    [TargetRpc]
    public void TargetHealed(int amount)
    {
        // No NetworkConnection parameter, so it goes to owner
        Debug.Log($"Health increased by {amount}");
    }
}
```

Figure 6: Server-Side Command and TargetRpc Interaction in Unity Mirror

SYNCVARS

SyncVars are properties of classes that inherit from `NetworkBehaviour`, which are synchronized from the server to clients. When a game object is spawned, or a new player joins a game in progress, they are sent the latest state of all SyncVars on networked objects that are visible to them. Use the `SyncVar` custom attribute to specify which variables in your script you want to synchronize.

The state of SyncVars is applied to game objects on clients before `OnStartClient()` is called, so the state of the object is always up-to-date inside `OnStartClient()`.

SyncVars can use any type supported by Mirror. You can have up to 64 SyncVars on a single `NetworkBehaviour` script, including SyncLists (see next section, below).

The server automatically sends SyncVar updates when the value of a SyncVar changes, so you do not need to track when they change or send information about the changes yourself. Changing a value in the inspector will not trigger an update. The `SyncVar` hook attribute can be used to specify a method to be called when the SyncVar changes value on the client.

Example:

```
SyncVars work with class inheritance. Consider this example:

class Pet : NetworkBehaviour
{
    [SyncVar]
    string name;
}

class Cat : Pet
{
    [SyncVar]
    public Color32 color;
}

You can attach the Cat component to your cat prefab, and it will synchronize both it's name and color.
```

Figure 7: Example of SyncVar Usage with Class Inheritance in Unity Mirror

(*SyncVars | Mirror*, 2021)

ORDER OF EVENTS

Mirror's Order of Events

Much like Unity, which has `Awake`, `Start`, `OnTriggerEnter`, and many others, Mirror Networking also has events. These events get invoked throughout the lifecycle of a Mirror Networking instance.

The events occur in the following order:

- `Awake (Unity)`
- `OnStartServer`
- `OnRebuildObservers`
- `OnStartAuthority`
- `OnStartClient`
- `OnSetHostVisibility`
- `OnStartLocalPlayer`
- `Start (Unity)`

You can access these methods by overriding the method within any `Network Behavior`. Let's take a look at each of these events and see where we might use them.

(Dylan Engelbrecht, 2021)

Figure 8: Execution Order of Network Manager and Network Behaviour in Unity Mirror

(Execution Order | Mirror, 2021)

UNITY:

Unity 6 is my preferred game engine of choice, because of its rich amount of features, familiarity, C# scripting, component-based, customizability (even the editor and render pipelines), large amount of existing assets, track record, community support, easy integrations, 2D and 3D, etc.

Especially with the new Unity 6 updates and roadmap revealed, it is looking very promising for Unity and I really like how the splash screen can be toggled off for free now (no need to have a unity subscription/license, as it used to be).

If you know C#, you will understand most of the code snippets without many issues. The only concepts that may be foreign are surrounding GameObjects (objects in the scene which inherit from MonoBehaviour, which can have components attached to them). These objects will always be (destroyed and) recreated on scene (re)load, unless they are marked with [DontDestroyOnLoad], which makes it persist across scenes.

Another thing that may be foreign for beginning Unity developers are Coroutines, which allows you to spread tasks across several frames. A coroutine is a method that can pause execution and return control to Unity but then continue where it left off on the following frame. (Technologies, n.d.)

CSHARP:

In this paper, I will not provide instruction on basic C# programming. It is assumed that the reader has a foundational understanding of Unity's workflow and the C# language. Instead, I will focus on discussing more advanced programming concepts that are relevant to implementing complex multiplayer features, such as host migration. These topics will be briefly explained to provide context for their use in game development.

REFLECTION

Reflection in C# is a powerful feature that allows a program to inspect and manipulate its own structure at runtime. It enables developers to access metadata about assemblies, types, methods, and properties dynamically. This is particularly useful in game development for creating flexible systems that can adapt to various game states without hardcoding behavior. For example, reflection can be used to invoke methods or access private fields, making it helpful for serialization, debugging, or implementing plugins. (BillWagner, 2023)

CODE INJECTION

In game development, particularly within Unity, code injection refers to the practice of dynamically modifying or extending the behavior of existing code during development. This technique is often employed through editor scripts to automate tasks, enhance workflows, or insert benchmarking code into existing scripts.

Implementing Code Injection in Unity

Unity's editor scripting capabilities allow developers to create custom tools and automate processes within the Unity Editor. By writing editor scripts, you can programmatically modify existing C# scripts to inject additional

code, such as benchmarking functions. This approach streamlines the development process and ensures consistency across the codebase.

INHERITANCE

Inheritance is a fundamental principle of object-oriented programming (OOP) in C#. It allows a class (child) to inherit properties and methods from another class (parent). In Unity, inheritance is widely used to create hierarchical structures where general behaviors are defined in base classes and specific behaviors are implemented in derived classes. For instance, a general Enemy class can define basic movement, while subclasses like FlyingEnemy or GroundEnemy can extend or override that behavior. (BillWagner, 2023)

COST ANALYSIS

Small-Scale Dedicated Servers: For less resource-intensive games or smaller player groups, dedicated server rentals can start around \$5 to \$50 per month. These servers are suitable for hosting games like Minecraft or Terraria with a limited number of players and bandwidth used. These costs wildly vary between providers. (Game Server Rental, 2024; Tuwiner, 2024)

Medium to Large Dedicated Servers: For more demanding games or larger player bases, costs can range from \$15 to \$100 per month. Survival games like ARK: Survival Evolved or Rust typically fall into this category, requiring more robust hardware to ensure smooth gameplay. (Tuwiner, 2024)

Massively Multiplayer Online (MMO) Servers: Hosting servers for MMOs, which support thousands of concurrent players, can be significantly more expensive. Monthly costs may range from a few hundred to several thousand dollars, depending on the number of players and server efficiency. For instance, supporting around 5,000 concurrent players might cost approximately \$1,500 per month. (Tuwiner, 2024)

The cost of a game server depends on the game you're playing, the total number of concurrent players, and some other factors (like the cost of electricity where your game host is located).

Here are some of the basic factors that impact the cost of game hosting:

- CPU power
- RAM
- Storage
- Network speed
- Operating System

As your server scales in size (higher concurrent player count), you'll need more of the server's resources outlined above, which will raise your rental fee. (Tuwiner, 2024)

HOST MIGRATION BASIC EXPLANATION:

Host migration is a feature in online multiplayer games that allows a game to continue smoothly when the player hosting the game leaves or disconnects.

In many multiplayer games, one player acts as the host, meaning their computer or console is responsible for running the game world and managing connections with other players. If this host leaves the game or their internet connection drops, the game could crash or disconnect everyone.

Host migration solves this problem by automatically selecting a new player to take over as the host. The game quickly transfers all the necessary data to the new host so that the game continues without ending the session for other players.

Example:

- You and your friends are playing a co-op survival game.
- One player is the host, managing the game world.
- If the host's internet goes down, the game chooses another player to become the new host.
- The game continues without kicking anyone out, and everyone keeps playing.

This is a great QOL (quality of life) feature which is requested by many players out of communities of games which utilise player-hosted architecture, without having a working host migration solution.

RESEARCH

This section outlines the research methodology and experimental processes undertaken to evaluate the feasibility of implementing host migration in online multiplayer co-op games using Unity and Mirror Netcode. The research involved developing a functional game prototype, conducting extensive testing with various network transports, and implementing and benchmarking host migration.

1. GAME PROTOTYPE

1.1. WHY?

To better understand the practical challenges of implementing host migration, I developed a game prototype—a simple dice game designed for two to four players (See Appendix 1). This prototype aimed to become more familiar with Mirror and explore how synchronizing game states works in practice with actual game architecture. The game allowed players to join the lobby, ready up, move around, roll dice, deal damage and take damage from enemies (show health bars), die, fight waves with bosses, each wave progressively gets harder, pick and save a random booster of their choice, and reset the game if they lost, to simulate a real production-scope game, in an early phase.

The dice game was successfully built for LAN and Steam, using the developer steam appid: 480 (Spacewar). Implementing the restart feature offered valuable insights into how game state synchronization must be carefully handled to maintain consistency across all clients, especially when transitioning between rounds or resetting the game state.

Some screenshots showing how the prototype looks:

Players hitting enemies for 13 damage (6 + 1 + 6). The previous enemies have already died, the leftovers count up.

Players beat a wave, and have the option to pick a booster card.

Players just killed an enemy, as you can see the left player picked More Dice, and the right player picked Glass Cannon (he lost half of his health, and now deals double damage).

Figure 9: Prototype Gameplay Progression Demonstrating Enemy Damage, Booster Selection, and Wave Advancement

This development process showed me some very valuable revelations, such as that there will be client and server side information intertwined everywhere. Another interesting finding was that the principle of “Server runs the game, client runs the show” will lead you to implement a server authoritative architecture, where some data about players will not be stored on each client, but on the client object’s copy on the server. This makes a big difference when having to sync this over post host migration.

What would make my thesis really useful to the community of developers is how a host migration system would integrate into an actual production-sized game; is it possible to get away with “just adding it at the end”? How does it actually work? That’s what is actually important, so I believe it makes sense to get some sort of prototype ready, so my experiments aren’t in vain. What is it worth after all, if it only works in a sandbox of data containers and transforms? So, I made a game where it would make sense for a lack of host migration to be detrimental to the player experience (imagine you’re playing in one session for an hour, and the host’s Wi-Fi cuts out for a minute...)

1.2. GAME CONCEPT

I needed to make a very basic co-op game to test the features out. It should have a short, intuitive loop for any reader of this paper to understand easily and a good example of where host migration might be useful.

After some brainstorming, I came up with this:

Game idea: Co-op dice roguelike (2-4 players):

Every player has one dice, and they have to work together by rolling the dice in a turn. The number of eyes in total rolled get counted, and that’s the damage the group does. There is an enemy, who has a number of health points, and receives the damage dealt by the group. If he stays alive that turn, he does some damage to all players. If he dies, the players move along to the next enemy; same thing. After 5 enemies, a boss comes along. This boss is harder to beat, and if the players beat it, they each get to pick a random booster. The game gets harder every round, so strategic booster picking is important to survive as long as possible. Surviving as many waves as possible is the goal of the game.

Some booster card ideas I implemented (architected in code in a production-ready way for added realism):

Common:

Regenerate: Regenerate your player health (one-time-use)

Lifesteal: Heal back 15% of the damage done to enemies permanently

Saviour: Revive a random dead player (one-time-use)

Healthy: Give yourself 20 extra health points permanently

Legendary:

Dice: Give yourself another dice permanently

Chaotic:

Glass cannon: Deal double damage forever, in exchange for half of your health points.

I created this game, much of the code working with Commands, RPCs, and SyncVars. Enemies had to spawn on runtime, which I did through NetworkServer.Spawn on the server. All game state (the turns, waves, etc.) are

managed by the server and the UI is locally done through the clients, as it should be in a real game. Remember: Server runs the game, clients run the show. Even though we're not concerned with cheating, there are thousands of ways to implement a feature and to keep things organized it's good practice to stick to one principle.

1.3. PROJECT SETUP

For readers looking to get started with mirror and start developing something themselves, I created a small start-up guide for LAN multiplayer. This could very easily be changed to another transport and platform, but would require a few more installations.

You can follow the step-by-step guide in Appendix 2 at the bottom of this paper.

2. EXPERIMENTATION AND NEWFOUND INFORMATION

2.1. ISSUES WITH DIRECT CONNECTIONS

While searching through forum posts and the mirror discord for more information, I stumbled upon the fact that directly connecting players through peer-to-peer networking would require port forwarding and NAT traversal, both of which are impractical to expect from the average player. Even if all of my players were experienced with their network and had access to the network administrator account, their ISP could still block them from doing this.

2.2. RELAY INTERMEDIARY SOLUTION

This constraint led me to explore relay solutions, which act as an intermediary, making it so I don't need to expect any port mapping or NAT from the players. As I am looking to primarily help out independent game developers, I explored only free solutions, as this is the whole point: not bleeding money on servers we have to support for many years. The only working free relays I found were Steam and Epic Games relays.

Before I started developing the host migration solution, I experimented with different network transports to identify the most reliable and practical solution for implementing host migration. Initially, I tested KCP transport, the default transport for Mirror, inspired by the host migration example from AlexRak2, which was limited to LAN environments. As I had already made a prototype on Steam prior to this research, I knew this was feasible and how to do it – no experimentation was needed. However, through extensive research—including numerous forum threads, Discord discussions in the Mirror community and documentation—I discovered that the EOS Transport was unreliable for production use. Many people were having issues with it, because sudden downtimes are commonplace and setting it up is more difficult. As a free relay service, it lacked comprehensive documentation and consistent maintenance, leading to frequent issues.

After getting a connection through EOS working, I tried to do it on Steam again and was shocked at how much easier it was. One twelve minute tutorial from HomeSliceDev later and my game was up and running again via the Steam relay. (Home Slice Game Dev, 2023)

My research, testing and previous experience thus led me to the conclusion that Steam's networking infrastructure was far more stable and user-friendly compared to Epic's, making it the better choice for reliable multiplayer connectivity. It's easier to develop for, with more resources available to learn from and more developers using it.

To aid in debugging, especially in Steam builds, I developed a custom on-screen debugger script. This tool displayed real-time feedback on errors, and warnings and logs automatically, with appropriate colouring, significantly improving the development process by allowing me to identify and resolve issues in builds more efficiently.

You can view this script and use it in your own projects in Appendix 1: Github repository at the bottom of the paper.

3. HOST MIGRATION

3.1. OBJECTIVES

The core objective of this research was to implement and evaluate a functional host migration system. I focused on understanding the differences between client-side and server-side data synchronization and how these differences impact the migration process. Managing different types of data across different sessions presented some challenges due to the ways Mirror handles data synchronization.

Side objectives consisted of making it scalable (as this is one of the most important factors when considering the migration: "would it work in a large-scale co-op game?"), easy to implement for developers and efficient. For this reason, I minimized the amount of hacky solutions, aiming to make a solution that could actually be used by studios across the world.

3.2. HOW IT'S DONE

The host migration can be divided into two categories: client-side (local) and server-side information. These both need to be synced and usually have two different use cases. Client-side info is anything that the client can be trusted with, or that the client synchronizes to the server. An example of this could be its position and rotation. Server-side info is anything that the host keeps, this would traditionally be sensitive information like player health, the wave state you're currently on, or how many cards or dice the players have. Each player is given a UCID (unique client identifier), as netIds and SyncVars get reset upon migration and we need to synchronize each player with their corresponding saved data. If the players' data is scrambled because the netIds are scrambled, it would be extremely confusing. Each client is appointed this UCID, and it is kept upon migration. No two players can have the same UCID in the same session – no matter what happens.

MIGRATING TO A NEW SESSION

Without concern of any data synchronization, let's discuss the actual migration:

When the host disconnects, the clients need to know who is responsible for hosting the next session. The backup host, with responsibility of starting the new game, will start a coroutine which will start up their client as the host after a small delay. The clients will start a coroutine which sets their network address to connect to in the network

manager to the new host's address and after a small delay join as a client. This is all tested locally first in the editor, using the ParrelSync tool to open multiple clones of the same project, allowing for easier debugging.

This is what the host migration looks like in build, you can see four builds open, each has authority over their own cube (player) which can move around and gets designated a UCID (Unique Client Identifier) which ensures that their data is synchronized correctly. This is visually shown by attaching a colour to it. When the host leaves, all players lose connection

As you can see, all of the cubes are gone, as the host just disconnected. Thanks to host migration, the coroutines are started and the host starts up a new session, which the clients quickly join.

After the remaining clients have joined, you can see that the color is not yet assigned; this still needs to be synchronized, it is the duration that will be benchmarked as well (= the retrieval of data post migration)

The clients have received all of their data and have automatically updated it again, approximately a second later.

Figure 10: Players rejoined post host migration and have resynchronized all of their data

CLIENT-SIDE INFORMATION

Client-side information synchronization is the easy part: assuming that the clients don't quit the game, their data will be stored locally on a component on the Network Manager. This is a GameObject in the scene, with a

NetworkManager component. This GameObject has the DontDestroyOnLoad method activated, which makes it so this object (as well as its attached components) persists through scene changes. This makes it perfect for local data storage for sessions: when the player quits, it's gone, but when they get kicked because the host disconnected, it stays intact. The key is to save the data OnDestroy() from all scripts with any information you want to carry over to the new session, saving them to the HostMigrationData component. When the player connects back, check if there is any data and if there is, you load it. If there isn't any data, that means the game just started for the first time.

SERVER-SIDE INFORMATION

Server-side information synchronization is a little bit harder: the hosting client (= the server) leaves the game, but he is the only one who has the server-only data. We cannot save anything locally on this hosting client, because quite frankly, he will be gone and so will the corresponding data. The solution is to synchronize the server-only data over to a backup host preemptively, so in the case of any unexpected game crash or wifi outage it's not too late to send over the new data. Sending it over preemptively can be done in one of two ways: based on an interval, or incrementally every time there's new information. For the purpose of having a scalable, reliable system, I've decided to go for the incremental instantaneous method. This way, there can be no data lost due to the interval being last called a few seconds before the migration, for example. In those few seconds, a lot could have happened that changed the course of a game. I'll call this incremental increase method the co-host method from now on, as you constantly send the server-data to another player, as if they are already co-hosting the server with you. When your connection falls away, they simply step up and use the information that you have been sharing with them all this time. This doesn't sound too difficult in practice, but here is where it gets a little bit harder:

What if the server data is not just state only, but also contains some secret fields or variables that only the server may know about the other players? Well, the server would have information stored or set containing the fields of other people. Unfortunately, after the session ends and another scene starts to fill its place, the references to these fields or objects are gone forever. There are multiple solutions to tackle this, but I went for the solution which is the easiest for other developers to use, regardless of what game they're making. I use a reflection-based approach, storing the data as a string about the name of the field, component of the field, type of the field and the value of the field in the HostMigrationData component on the Network Manager of the new host. This makes it so the data struct is easy to save and transfer across the network (only serialized types with primitive structures or things composed of primitives can be sent over the network, an example of a primitive are most standard C# types like int, float, string, etc.). It does not matter whether the developer is trying to save an interface, a class, a custom struct, or anything like that. The developer simply saves the things needed to reference that exact field. After the host disconnects, the new host already owns all of the data in their HostMigrationData class, but the data is not yet synced to the correct locations. To sync them, we loop through all of the MigrationData stored and use C# reflection to assign back all of the values to the correct fields on the correct objects. This is a slow process, but thankfully host-migration should not happen too often for it to be an issue. When this is done, all server-side information is synced.

3.3 BENCHMARKING

Benchmarking the results was quite the challenge:

- Methods run asynchronously, sometimes spanning across clients or sessions
- Methods don't have one end-point, so stopping the benchmark sometimes requires multiple end-points to be reached, requiring me to make a custom Stopwatch class.
- Data was so small to start of with that I needed to calculate everything to microseconds for good accuracy

- Need to have two editors running at all times
- Data can be inconsistent for many reasons, so need to have a decent sample size
- Getting the data for the large cases can take over thirty seconds per datum
- I needed to modify KCP (the network transport code) to stop disconnections from happening, as sometimes it would take so long to process that the host became unresponsive and triggered a quit event.
- There are lots of factors going into it that I cannot control (latency, network usage, JIT (Just In Time) compilation, optimizing away my testing code, random network spikes or computer lags, ...)
- Garbage collection needed to be managed manually to avoid buildup skewing results
- BenchmarkDotNet, the C# library I was planning to use, does not support Unity
- I wrote the migration code in a scalable way, which made testing the server-side information more challenging: just updating a variable a million times wasn't going to cut it. The code made it so that the game would automatically save the last value assigned and only read that variable.
- This made it so I needed to have thousands of fields, with different names to loop through with reflection
- Making thousands of fields needed to be done with a custom made code injection tool to be efficient

Alright, now that you know the difficulties, how did I handle this?

PREVENTION FOR MORE ACCURATE RESULTS:

- Closed all other apps running for all measurements
- Restarted the editor's play mode halfway through each test
- Sample sizes of 20+ data members for client, 10+ for server (for each value)
- Manual garbage collection before and after each benchmark
- Fighting the JIT compiler by making the data actually do something so it doesn't get optimized away
- Saving directly to a csv file with all statistics to prevent human error
- Tested everything on LAN to prevent latency increases
- Ensuring testing is done properly in the right order by tracking each step in a notebook

You can view the custom benchmarking tools in Appendix 1: GitHub repository at the bottom of the paper

WHAT EXACTLY WAS TESTED?

The duration in microseconds for the retrieval of data from the host migration was tested for both client-side information and server-side information (See appendix 3 and 4). The data was retrieved separately, making for an opportunity to compare how efficient both options are. If somebody is inspired by this paper and wants to limit-test the host migration for a large scale game, the segregation between the two leaves them the option to use the faster method more often.

ANALYSIS

The data was analyzed statistically using R with regression analysis, plotted out on a graph.


```
> client_reg_form
[1] "Log10_Duration = 6.13585309 + 0.0170757 * Log10_Extra_Packets + e"
```

Figure 11: Impact of Increasing Client-Side Data on Synchronization Duration. Log-log plot showing the relationship between the amount of client-side data (in extra bytes/packets) and the synchronization duration (in microseconds). Data was tested up to two gigabytes per client, approaching the array byte size limit in C#. The red regression line represents the fitted model: $\text{Log}_{10}(\text{Duration}) = 6.13585309 + 0.0170757 \times \text{Log}_{10}(\text{Extra_Packets}) + e$. The graph highlights a steady increase in synchronization time as data size grows, with a noticeable spike beyond realistic data limits.

Client-side information was tested up to two gigabytes of client data per client. This happens to be the array byte size limit in C# and already way above any realistic amount of data. To put it into perspective, this would be the equivalent of storing more than 166 million fields with Vector3s. It is possible to test beyond this, but there really is no point.

Figure 12: Linear Relationship Between Extra Bytes/Packets and Synchronization Duration in Microseconds for Client-side Info

> server_reg_form

```
[1] "Log10_Duration = 3.79503451 + 0.68479369 * Log10_Extra_Packets + e"
```

Figure 13: Impact of Increasing Server-Side Data on Synchronization Duration. Log-log plot illustrating the relationship between extra bytes/packets and server-side synchronization duration (in microseconds). The red regression line shows the fitted model: $\text{Log}_{10}(\text{Duration}) = 3.79503451 + 0.68479369 \times \text{Log}_{10}(\text{Extra_Packets}) + e$. The results indicate a stronger positive correlation between increased data size and synchronization time on the server side, with synchronization duration rising more rapidly compared to the client-side performance.

Figure 14: Linear Relationship between Extra bytes/packets and Synchronization Duration in microseconds for Server-side Info

You can view the raw data gathered in Appendix 3: Benchmark raw data at the bottom of the paper

DISCUSSION

From the results of the benchmarking, it shows that there is a large amount of data that you can transfer for almost no performance cost across migrations. The differences in duration for synchronizing both client and server side information are practically negligible, when looking in realistic ranges (you likely won't be syncing two gigabytes of data, and even then it is still very performant) . Client-side information is easier to store and retrieve, as it relates to the client's owned objects, which can be referenced with ease. Thus, allowing for data synchronization without a need for C# reflection, which is slower and takes up more space.

Server-side information needs to make use of reflection as data needs to be networked to the backup host(s). This is because commands and remote procedure calls only support networking primitives, or serialized classes and components built up out of primitives out of the box, which is a limitation that would make it more difficult for other developers to integrate host migration. (*Data Types | Mirror, 2024*)

Expecting the adaptors of this asset to create custom network writers and readers is not worth the small performance tradeoff, as the data analysis shows (you can send up to 2690 fields at once in under a second, trying to send more at once is prevented by Mirror's max batch size). For games larger in scope, this is merely a theoretical limit (because of the maximum packet batch size to send over the network) which can easily be circumvented by integrating a system which splits up the batches and reorders them on retrieval. I'm sure this solution can still be optimized, allowing for better server-side scalability. It's important to keep in mind that just sending a singular byte this way, needs to hold five strings (client identifier, component, variable, type, value), which can make the actual packet size over 100 bytes, depending on the string length. (Crease, 2009)

The data of clients is independent of how many players are in a session, while the server-side data could show at worst a linear increase with player count, if all server-data is confidential information relative to all clients. This all depends on each individual game and how much confidential information the server holds for other clients. To optimize the speed and reliability of the host migration, it is recommended to store as much information as possible on each client locally; this minimizes bandwidth usage and allows for a larger scale with a very favorable scaling coefficient (retrieving 2 gigabytes of data takes less than double the time of retrieving 1 byte of data – this is a 200.000.000.000% increase of data, with a timespan increase of less than 100%) (see Figures 10–12 for more details).

The long duration of synchronizing a small amount of bytes can be attributed to the fact that Commands and RPCs have to finish running, passing between players' devices across the network. These methods will always have a substantial running time, as they jump between networks and devices, which is unavoidable. (Shelton, 2022)

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, a scalable host migration system was created successfully in Unity 6 utilizing Mirror for networking. It was tested thoroughly for both LAN through KCP transport and online multiplayer through Steam transport with FizzySteamworks routing packets through the SDR (Steam Datagram Relay). (*Steam Datagram Relay (Steamworks Documentation)*, n.d.)

372 entries of raw data were collected on the duration of synchronization of data with varying byte sizes, for both client and server separately. Additionally, they were analyzed in R with regression analysis, which showcased how far the theoretical limits of this current implementation can go. However, this solution could be driven further after optimizations and refactors allowing for networked packets to be split up and reordered later, in turn vastly increasing the potential maximum data transferred.

To answer the research questions:

In which contexts is host migration a feasible solution in game development for online multiplayer co-op games?

Host migration is a feasible solution for online multiplayer co-op games that are not concerned with the users being able to cheat and the time spent migrating is not a game breaking issue. I would not recommend it for games heavily reliant on physics interactions, as across scene transfers it will prove difficult to have physics immediately continuing reliably for all players. Data shows that the scale of the game will not be an important factor for the migration time, but the larger the scope of the game, the more data will need to be saved and reinstated correctly, which could hinder development time. For this reason I would not recommend it for MMOs, RPGs or any large production games. I see it as a worthy solution for small and mid-sized games, especially for indie developers who might otherwise struggle with the server upkeep costs, making game development more sustainable for them.

What are the most effective strategies for implementing host migration in a player-hosted (client-server) architecture for online multiplayer co-op games for indie studios using Unity?

From my experience developing and researching in this project, I believe the following is fundamental to ensure a simple, yet sophisticated host migration system can be created:

- **Network transports:** KCP for LAN and Steam transport for Steam
KCP is simple and fast to set up and use and the use of a relay server is needed to avoid NAT and security issues and port forwarding for your users. There are many options for relay servers, but for a free relay SDR is the best out there, from my experience.
- **Client-side info:** stored locally
The data shows this is a fantastic way of doing it, minimizing bandwidth, being fast and reliable.
- **Server-side info:** reflection based
There will certainly be faster algorithms to do this. Fortunately, host migration should not be a hot path in your game, which allows us to optimize for developer manhours instead of runtime performance. Data shows that it is feasible for a large number of fields (2690), without any further optimizations needed. This number is dependent on your exact implementation and what data you're storing (as it's string-based).

- **Designating a backup host:** one future host is fine
I was uncertain at first if there should be an ordered list of future backup hosts, or just one. I believe that the edge-case of both the host and a client leaving at the exact same time is not worth spending extra development time on, as this will almost never happen. Even if this were to happen, given you are developing a small to mid-sized game, a large fraction of your session's players will be gone and the remaining clients won't be as frustrated with the situation.
- **Syncing interval:** co-host is more suitable
I believe that it is better for the user experience that the game does not send full game saves over a long interval, as then a lot of progress could be lost (Photon's current method). Additionally, I don't think it is worth the extra development time creating a batch system that will store data and send it to the backup host on a short interval, as you could still lose data, and would have to revert the client state to the state they had at the time of the server-syncing interval. This seems impractical and less reliable, which is why I believe sending incremental data to the backup host as soon as it happens is the most optimal solution. This ensures a complete migration without loss of data and less upfront development time.
- **Starting early:** definitely recommended
As with many things multiplayer, don't add it at the end. This might cause you a lot of frustration. Decide at the start of your project if it is worth it to implement and if it is, implement it immediately so you can simply add on to it whenever you are implementing a new feature. This will save you lots of time refactoring later on in the development cycle.

FUTURE WORK

While this research has explored the feasibility of implementing host migration in online multiplayer co-op games developed with Unity, several areas remain open for further investigation and improvement. Addressing these limitations and exploring new strategies could significantly enhance the robustness and scalability of host migration systems.

SIMULTANEOUS HOST AND BACKUP HOST DISCONNECTION

One of the critical challenges in host migration is managing scenarios where both the primary host and the designated backup host disconnect simultaneously. The strategy discussed in this paper does not address this edge case, it only picks one backup host; however, this method is vulnerable if the host and backup host leave in the same timespan of a few seconds. Future research could explore dynamic host selection algorithms that continuously evaluate all connected clients based on their network stability and latency to determine the most suitable next host. Implementing some sort of ordered list of future hosts mechanism could minimize disruptions in these edge cases.

HANDLING LATE JOINERS

Integrating late joiners into an ongoing game session during or after a host migration poses synchronization and data consistency challenges. Future studies could focus on designing efficient state synchronization protocols that allow new players to seamlessly join games without causing performance bottlenecks or desynchronization issues. This could involve incremental state updates or lightweight data snapshots to ensure late joiners are quickly integrated into the game world.

REAL-WORLD CASE STUDY

A valuable extension of this research would be conducting a real-world case study by implementing and testing the proposed host migration solution in a production-size multiplayer game. Observing how these strategies perform under real-world conditions, such as varying network environments and server loads would provide critical insights into their practicality and effectiveness. This study did not make use of any object spawning, but a production game might – an easy solution could be a for loop through the `NetworkServer.spawned`, saving the information and later respawning the objects in their correct locations in the new session.

By addressing these areas, future research can build upon the foundational work presented in this study to create more resilient, efficient, and developer-friendly host migration systems for indie game developers and the broader gaming industry.

CRITICAL REFLECTION

Reflecting on the process of completing this research, I can confidently say that this project has been one of the most challenging yet rewarding experiences in my academic career as a programmer. Throughout this journey, I have improved my technical skills and enhanced my understanding of complex networking concepts.

One of the most valuable aspects of this project was the opportunity to become deeply familiar with Mirror and its networking code. Initially, I had only a surface-level understanding of multiplayer networking and programming, but through hands-on experimentation and implementation, I gained a much clearer understanding of how Mirror operates and how host migration can be realized.

The last three weeks of the project were especially intense. I dedicated countless hours to pushing this research forward, working 12-16 hours every single day to overcome technical hurdles and refine my implementations. This period of hard work was difficult, but it ultimately led to lots of character development and better time management skills. I learned how to break down complex problems into smaller, more manageable tasks and how to prioritize work effectively under pressure: I started using a notebook, actually writing stuff down on paper for the first time in years to break down difficult concepts and work it out step by step.

One of the initial challenges I faced was my lack of professional connections within the game development and networking fields. Being self-taught in the networking department, with few resources available to learn from (in retrospect, I should have gone through the Mirror official examples earlier...). However, as the project progressed, I began engaging with the Mirror community, participating in discussions, asking questions, and sharing insights. These interactions not only provided me with valuable feedback and solutions but also helped me build connections with experienced developers who offered guidance and support. This networking experience was an unexpected but welcome outcome of the project. I will likely make a game together with another developer from this community after this semester is done.

Looking back, I recognize that I overscoped the project. My initial goal was to implement host migration within a fully functional game prototype and test multiple migration strategies under different scenarios. However, I quickly realized that this approach was far beyond the scope of what was achievable within the given timeframe. This experience reiterated the importance of setting realistic goals and recognizing when to scale back to focus on delivering meaningful results.

Originally, I considered focusing on general multiplayer solutions for indie game developers—a much safer and more straightforward topic. However, I am glad I chose the more challenging path of innovating within host migration. This decision pushed me beyond my comfort zone and allowed me to tackle a problem that, while complex, has the potential to make a meaningful difference for indie developers seeking cost-effective multiplayer solutions. I hope this paper will open people's minds about the possibility of host migration, for more sustainable development of online multiplayer co-op games.

Throughout this project, I also developed several custom tools and systems that have greatly enhanced my library of useful snippets I can reuse in future projects. I created a benchmarking system to measure performance impacts, on-screen debugging tools for real-time feedback in builds, and custom Mirror debug classes to streamline testing and troubleshooting. I plan on releasing these tools into the public domain on YouTube in the future, to help out the community of game developers.

In conclusion, this research has been a pivotal learning experience, enabling me to grow as a programmer and developer. I have gained technical skills, developed critical problem-solving strategies, and connected with a

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community of like-minded developers. Despite the challenges and the initial overscope, I look back very fondly on this opportunity and the results accomplished. I'm excited to continue exploring innovative solutions in multiplayer game development and make many small games, kickstarting my career.

REFERENCES

- A Brief History of Mirror | Mirror*. (2023, December 13). <https://mirror-networking.gitbook.io/docs/trivia/a-history-of-mirror>
- BillWagner. (2023a, February 3). *Tutorial: Introduction to Inheritance - C#*. <https://learn.microsoft.com/en-us/dotnet/csharp/fundamentals/tutorials/inheritance>
- BillWagner. (2023b, March 15). *Attributes and reflection—C#*. <https://learn.microsoft.com/en-us/dotnet/csharp/advanced-topics/reflection-and-attributes/>
- Client-Server Architecture—System Design*. (2024). GeeksforGeeks. <https://www.geeksforgeeks.org/client-server-architecture-system-design/>
- Crease, J. (2009, January 16). How big is a string in .NET? *Simple Talk*. <https://www.red-gate.com/simple-talk/blogs/how-big-is-a-string-in-net/>
- Data types | Mirror*. (2024, January 30). <https://mirror-networking.gitbook.io/docs/manual/guides/data-types>
- Dongen, J. V. (2014, September 21). Joost's Dev Blog: Relay servers. *Joost's Dev Blog*. <https://joostdevblog.blogspot.com/2014/09/relay-servers.html>
- Dylan Engelbrecht. (2021). *Building Multiplayer Games in Unity: Using Mirror Networking*. Apress. <https://www.oreilly.com/library/view/building-multiplayer-games/9781484274743/>
- Execution Order | Mirror*. (2021, July 22). <https://mirror-networking.gitbook.io/docs/manual/faq/execution-order>
- FAQ | Mirror*. (2021, December 21). <https://mirror-networking.gitbook.io/docs/manual/faq>

Ferretti, S., & D'Angelo, G. (2018). Client/Server Gaming Architectures. In N. Lee (Ed.), *Encyclopedia of Computer Graphics and Games* (pp. 1–2). Springer International Publishing.

https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-08234-9_272-1

FishNet: Networking Evolved | Network | Unity Asset Store. (2024).

<https://assetstore.unity.com/packages/tools/network/fishnet-networking-evolved-207815?srltid=AfmBOqgb3U2zlxnihoA2UKpa5JKwTvmBG3QIMFiEQvMb4gdK4wKnLW>

FizzySteamworks Transport | Mirror. (2021, February 25). <https://mirror->

[networking.gitbook.io/docs/manual/transport/fizzysteamworks-transport](https://mirror-networking.gitbook.io/docs/manual/transport/fizzysteamworks-transport)

Fusion 2 Host Migration API | Photon Engine. (n.d.). Retrieved January 12, 2025, from

<https://doc.photonengine.com/fusion/current/manual/advanced/host-migration>

Game Server Rental: How Much Does Game Server Rental Cost. (2024, July 10). Pine Hosting Blog.

<https://pinehosting.com/blog/game-server-rentals-how-much-does-it-cost-to-rent-a-game-server/>

GDC 2025 (Director). (2018, July 26). *Denial of Service Mitigation* [Video recording].

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=2CQ1sxPppV4>

General | Mirror. (2024, March 21). <https://mirror-networking.gitbook.io/docs/manual/general>

Hoffmann, M. (2025). *Chykary/FizzySteamworks* [C#]. <https://github.com/Chykary/FizzySteamworks> (Original work published 2019)

Home Slice Game Dev (Director). (2023, July 16). *How To Connect to Steam In Unity with Mirror Networking— Multiplayer Game Tutorial Part 2* [Video recording].

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=tFnNfq_EWWM

Hoverflow on Steam. (2021). <https://store.steampowered.com/app/1280060/Hoverflow/>

How do community servers work? - Programming & Scripting / Multiplayer & Networking. (2021, September 17). Epic Developer Community Forums. <https://forums.unrealengine.com/t/how-do-community-servers-work/251231>

Internet Service Provider (ISP): What They Do and Examples. (2024). Investopedia. <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/i/isp.asp>

Is there really any point to making a client-server game authoritative? - Unity Engine. (2011, August 30). Unity Discussions. <https://discussions.unity.com/t/is-there-really-any-point-to-making-a-client-server-game-authoritative/454335>

KCP - A Fast and Reliable ARQ Protocol. (2024). GitHub. <https://github.com/skywind3000/kcp/blob/master/README.en.md>

KCP Transport | Mirror. (2022, June 19). <https://mirror-networking.gitbook.io/docs/manual/transports/kcp-transport>

Klimas, M. (2023, November 10). *Port forwarding for gaming.* Surfshark. <https://surfshark.com/blog/port-forwarding-for-gaming>

Kroupp, G. (2024, July 22). *Mastering Multiplayer Game Architecture: Choosing the Right Approach - Getgud.io.* <https://www.getgud.io/blog/mastering-multiplayer-game-architecture-choosing-the-right-approach/>, <https://www.getgud.io/blog/mastering-multiplayer-game-architecture-choosing-the-right-approach/>

Liar's Bar on Steam. (n.d.). Retrieved January 12, 2025, from https://store.steampowered.com/app/3097560/Liars_Bar/

Long list of networking solutions for Unity—Unity Engine. (2022, October 7). Unity Discussions. <https://discussions.unity.com/t/long-list-of-networking-solutions-for-unity/896525>

Maximum Packet Size for a TCP Connection | Baeldung on Computer Science. (n.d.). Retrieved January 12, 2025, from <https://www.baeldung.com/cs/tcp-max-packet-size>

Mildenberger, T. (2024, May 9). *Peer-to-Peer vs. Dedicated Server – A Comparison.* Blog. <https://contabo.com/blog/peer-to-peer-vs-dedicated-servers/>

Mirror | Network | Unity Asset Store. (2021). https://assetstore.unity.com/packages/tools/network/mirror-129321?srltid=AfmBOop_v8XrSo9EEZX-kYCoVv8X_efMBWPKZtG6OGAqhjh2eMBI8vi

MirrorNetworking/Mirror. (2025). [C#]. MirrorNetworking. <https://github.com/MirrorNetworking/Mirror>
(Original work published 2018)

Moore's law has accurately predicted the progress in transistor counts over the last 50 years. (n.d.). Our World in Data. Retrieved January 12, 2025, from <https://ourworldindata.org/data-insights/moores-law-has-accurately-predicted-the-progress-in-transistor-counts-over-the-last-50-years>

Multiplayer Game Development Made Easy | Photon Engine. (n.d.). Retrieved January 12, 2025, from <https://www.photonengine.com/>

Network Address Translation (NAT). (2024). GeeksforGeeks. <https://www.geeksforgeeks.org/network-address-translation-nat/>

Network Behaviour | Mirror. (2023, November 4). <https://mirror-networking.gitbook.io/docs/manual/components/networkbehaviour>

Networking Fundamentals: Every game developer Should Know. (2024, October 20). <https://gamedevguides.com/networking-fundamentals-every-game-developer-should-know/>

Online game. (2024). In *Wikipedia*. https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Online_game&oldid=1265850193

Peer-to-Peer (P2P) Architecture. (2024). GeeksforGeeks. <https://www.geeksforgeeks.org/peer-to-peer-p2p-architecture/>

Photon Fusion Pricing. (n.d.). Retrieved January 12, 2025, from <https://www.photonengine.com/fusion/pricing>

Photon Realtime Pricing. (n.d.). Retrieved January 12, 2025, from <https://www.photonengine.com/realtime/pricing>

Port (computer networking). (2025). In *Wikipedia*. [https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Port_\(computer_networking\)&oldid=1268264107](https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Port_(computer_networking)&oldid=1268264107)

Relay servers. (n.d.). Retrieved January 12, 2025, from <https://docs.unity.com/ugs/manual/relay/manual/relay-servers>

Remote Actions | Mirror. (2023, March 10). <https://mirror-networking.gitbook.io/docs/manual/guides/communications/remote-actions>

Seven Things you need to know about Game Server Hosting Orchestration for a great player experience. (2021, September 27). GamesIndustry.Biz. <https://www.gamesindustry.biz/seven-things-you-need-to-know-about-game-server-hosting-orchestration-for-a-great-player-experience>

Shelton, J. (2022, May 3). *Internet at the speed of light | Yale News.* <https://news.yale.edu/2022/05/03/internet-speed-light>

Sophie McEvoy. (2024, November 12). *Ubisoft faces lawsuit for allegedly misleading players by shutting down The Crew.* GamesIndustry.Biz. <https://www.gamesindustry.biz/ubisoft-faces-lawsuit-for-allegedly-misleading-players-by-shutting-down-the-crew>

Steam Curator: Self-Hosted Games. (n.d.). Retrieved January 12, 2025, from <https://store.steampowered.com/curator/41339173-Self-Hosted-Games/>

Steam Datagram Relay (Steamworks Documentation). (n.d.). Retrieved January 12, 2025, from

https://partner.steamgames.com/doc/features/multiplayer/steamdatagramrelay?utm_source=chatgpt.com

SyncVars | Mirror. (2021, March 29). [https://mirror-](https://mirror-networking.gitbook.io/docs/manual/guides/synchronization/syncvars)

[networking.gitbook.io/docs/manual/guides/synchronization/syncvars](https://mirror-networking.gitbook.io/docs/manual/guides/synchronization/syncvars)

Technologies, U. (n.d.). *Unity - Manual: Splitting tasks across frames*. Retrieved January 12, 2025, from

<https://docs.unity3d.com/6000.0/Documentation/Manual/coroutines.html>

TechTarget. (2020). *Server hardware timeline* [Online Image].

<https://www.techtarget.com/searchdatacenter/feature/Dive-into-the-history-of-server-hardware>

Tuwiner, J. (2024, January 22). *How Much Does a Game Server Cost in 2024? (Quick Answer)*.

<https://www.easypc.io/game-hosts/cost/>

Understanding Peer-to-peer Networking In Multiplayer Games. (2024, September 29). Peerdh.Com.

<https://peerdh.com/blogs/programming-insights/understanding-peer-to-peer-networking-in-multiplayer-games>

Understanding the Network Layer and IP: Routing, IPv4 vs IPv6, and Key Concepts Explained. (2024, December

7). DEV Community. https://dev.to/vignesh_j/understanding-the-network-layer-and-ip-routing-ipv4-vs-ipv6-and-key-concepts-explained-4ip0

Unity Networking Feature Comparison Matrix—CodeSmile. (2023, March 28).

<https://codesmile.de/2023/03/28/unity-networking-solutions-feature-comparison-matrix/>

Unity Realtime Multiplayer, Part 8: Exploring Ready-Made Networking Solutions | HackerNoon. (2023).

<https://hackernoon.com/unity-realtime-multiplayer-part-8-exploring-ready-made-networking-solutions>

Unity—Manual: Host Migration. (n.d.). Retrieved January 12, 2025, from

<https://docs.unity3d.com/550/Documentation/Manual/UNetHostMigration.html>

Watch List – Delisted Games. (2025, January 9). <https://delistedgames.com/watch-list/>

What Are Relays Servers for Multiplayer Games? A Peer-to-Peer Networking Guide. (n.d.). Edgegap. Retrieved January 12, 2025, from <https://edgegap.com/blog/what-are-relays-servers-for-multiplayer-games-a-peer-to-peer-networking-guide>

What is Peer-to-Peer Networking for Multiplayer Games? (n.d.). Retrieved January 12, 2025, from <https://edgegap.com/blog/what-is-peer-to-peer-networking-for-multiplayer-games>

What Is TCP/IP? (2024). Lifewire. <https://www.lifewire.com/what-is-tcp-ip-8693053>

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I would like to extend my gratitude towards MrGadget and JesusLuvYoooh from the Mirror developer team for helping me understand how to navigate Mirror and networking in games. The patience and kindness with which I was treated (without being a supporter/sponsor/donator) has been unparalleled from any other developer community I have been a part of.

I would like to thank Sara Majid for helping with the statistics about my data, programming in R and carrying out the regression analysis with me.

APPENDICES

Appendix 1: Github repository

Appendix 2: Project setup

Appendix 3: Benchmarking raw data

Appendix 4: R code for data analysis

APPENDIX 1: GITHUB REPOSITORY

<https://github.com/LouisVanh/Host-Migration/>

APPENDIX 2: PROJECT SETUP

Install Unity 6000.0.32f1 LTS.

Launch project

Install Mirror via Unity Asset Store

Install ParrelSync via git (<https://github.com/VeriorPies/ParrelSync>)

If you want to develop for Steam, there are these installs you need:

Install FizzySteamworks via git (<https://github.com/Chykary/FizzySteamworks/releases>)

Install Steamworks.NET via git <https://github.com/r1abrecque/Steamworks.NET/releases>

Install Steamworks.NET SteamManager (this is required) via git <https://github.com/r1abrecque/Steamworks.NET-SteamManager/blob/master/SteamManager.cs>

Started up a new scene.

Added an empty object in hierarchy called MyNetworkManagerLAN.

Added a new script for a custom network manager:

```
using System.Collections;
```

```
using System.Collections.Generic;
```

```
using UnityEngine;
```

```
using Mirror;
```

```
public class MyNetworkManager : NetworkManager
```

```
{
```

```
    public override void OnStartServer()
```

```
    {
```

```
        Debug.Log("Server Started!");
```

```
    }
```

```
    public override void OnServerAddPlayer(NetworkConnectionToClient conn)
```


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Created a new 3D GameObject: Cube in the hierarchy.

Renamed it to Player.

Added Network Identity component to Player.

Created a new script: PlayerMovement

```
using UnityEngine;
```

```
using Mirror;
```

```
public class PlayerMove : NetworkBehaviour
```

```
{
```

```
    [SerializeField] private float _speed = 2.5f; // Default value, overrideable in engine
```

```
    private void Update()
```

```
    {
```

```
        if (isLocalPlayer)
```

```
        {
```

```
            float h = Input.GetAxis("Horizontal");
```

```
            float v = Input.GetAxis("Vertical");
```

```
            Vector3 playerMovement = new(h * _speed * Time.deltaTime, v * _speed * Time.deltaTime, 0);
```

```
            transform.position = transform.position + playerMovement;
```

```
        }
```

```
    }
```

```
}
```

Added the PlayerMovement script to the Player.

Made the player a prefab by dragging it into the Prefabs folder.

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Removed the object from the scene.

Dragged the prefab into the MyNetworkManagerLAN player slot.

Make sure Auto Create Player is ticked in the MyNetworkManagerLAN.

Added Network Transform (Reliable) component to the Player.

Start second client with the tab ParrelSync –) Clones Manager

Run the game on both instances (Start play-mode)

First player selects host, second selects client.

Move around using the arrow keys/WASD.

Success!

APPENDIX 3: BENCHMARK RAW DATA

Timestamp	Players	Sync_Method	Extra_Packets	Duration_Microseconds
11/01/2025 05:24	2	Client-side info	1	1435594
11/01/2025 05:24	2	Client-side info	1	1444077.9
11/01/2025 05:24	2	Client-side info	1	1428037.1
11/01/2025 05:24	2	Client-side info	1	1426464.1
11/01/2025 05:25	2	Client-side info	1	1424402.6
11/01/2025 05:25	2	Client-side info	1	1431667.8

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11/01/2025 05:25	2	Client-side info	1	1428395.8
11/01/2025 05:25	2	Client-side info	1	1433880.6
11/01/2025 05:26	2	Client-side info	1	1429286.4
11/01/2025 05:26	2	Client-side info	1	1428820.8
11/01/2025 05:27	2	Client-side info	1	1439703.3
11/01/2025 05:27	2	Client-side info	1	1442269.6
11/01/2025 05:27	2	Client-side info	1	1428929.5
11/01/2025 05:27	2	Client-side info	1	1419367.4
11/01/2025 05:27	2	Client-side info	1	1421949.4
11/01/2025 05:28	2	Client-side info	1	1427874.6
11/01/2025 05:28	2	Client-side info	1	1414717.5
11/01/2025 05:28	2	Client-side info	1	1419875.5
11/01/2025 05:28	2	Client-side info	1	1418699.8

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11/01/2025 05:28	2	Client-side info	1	1422293.6
11/01/2025 05:34	2	Client-side info	100	1432799.4
11/01/2025 05:34	2	Client-side info	100	1448371.3
11/01/2025 05:35	2	Client-side info	100	1420945
11/01/2025 05:35	2	Client-side info	100	1441715.4
11/01/2025 05:35	2	Client-side info	100	1423781.3
11/01/2025 05:36	2	Client-side info	100	1438059.4
11/01/2025 05:36	2	Client-side info	100	1442662.4
11/01/2025 05:36	2	Client-side info	100	1425207.1
11/01/2025 05:36	2	Client-side info	100	1426073.6
11/01/2025 05:36	2	Client-side info	100	1449227.6
11/01/2025 05:37	2	Client-side info	100	1432047.4
11/01/2025 05:37	2	Client-side info	100	1429526

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11/01/2025 05:38	2	Client-side info	100	1442265.2
11/01/2025 05:38	2	Client-side info	100	1436048.1
11/01/2025 05:38	2	Client-side info	100	1432833.1
11/01/2025 05:38	2	Client-side info	100	1440367.8
11/01/2025 05:38	2	Client-side info	100	1425953.3
11/01/2025 05:38	2	Client-side info	100	1429958.1
11/01/2025 05:39	2	Client-side info	100	1431739.4
11/01/2025 05:39	2	Client-side info	100	1426286
11/01/2025 05:42	2	Client-side info	10000	1428717.5
11/01/2025 05:43	2	Client-side info	10000	1432395.6
11/01/2025 05:43	2	Client-side info	10000	1441288.9
11/01/2025 05:43	2	Client-side info	10000	1423901.2
11/01/2025 05:43	2	Client-side info	10000	1417820.9

Vanhove Louis

11/01/2025 05:43	2	Client-side info	10000	1420247.2
11/01/2025 05:44	2	Client-side info	10000	1420201.1
11/01/2025 05:44	2	Client-side info	10000	1418658.7
11/01/2025 05:44	2	Client-side info	10000	1427512.4
11/01/2025 05:44	2	Client-side info	10000	1436770.7
11/01/2025 05:46	2	Client-side info	10000	1429816.4
11/01/2025 05:46	2	Client-side info	10000	1441188.8
11/01/2025 05:46	2	Client-side info	10000	1430455.1
11/01/2025 05:46	2	Client-side info	10000	1417954.2
11/01/2025 05:47	2	Client-side info	10000	1425265.3
11/01/2025 05:47	2	Client-side info	10000	1428520.8
11/01/2025 05:47	2	Client-side info	10000	1428574.5
11/01/2025 05:47	2	Client-side info	10000	1429696.5

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11/01/2025 05:47	2	Client-side info	10000	1421204.5
11/01/2025 05:47	2	Client-side info	10000	1432934.2
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11/01/2025 05:52	2	Client-side info	1000000	1430433.4
11/01/2025 05:52	2	Client-side info	1000000	1432255
11/01/2025 05:52	2	Client-side info	1000000	1442397.7
11/01/2025 05:53	2	Client-side info	1000000	1423831.1
11/01/2025 05:53	2	Client-side info	1000000	1438131.6
11/01/2025 05:53	2	Client-side info	1000000	1434139.3
11/01/2025 05:53	2	Client-side info	1000000	1450039.6
11/01/2025 05:54	2	Client-side info	1000000	1443939

Vanhove Louis

11/01/2025 05:54	2	Client-side info	1000000	1427175.8
11/01/2025 05:54	2	Client-side info	1000000	1434634.5
11/01/2025 05:54	2	Client-side info	1000000	1425689.6
11/01/2025 05:54	2	Client-side info	1000000	1424530.1
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11/01/2025 05:55	2	Client-side info	1000000	1436882.9
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11/01/2025 05:55	2	Client-side info	1000000	1450301
11/01/2025 05:55	2	Client-side info	1000000	1429850.5
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11/01/2025 07:09	2	Client-side info	1E+09	2120997.4
11/01/2025 07:14	2	Client-side info	1E+09	2085197.4
11/01/2025 07:14	2	Client-side info	1E+09	2178426.2

Vanhove Louis

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11/01/2025 07:19	2	Client-side info	1E+09	2196030.6
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11/01/2025 07:33	2	Client-side info	1E+09	2092271.6

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11/01/2025 05:25	2	Server-side info	1	293.8
11/01/2025 05:26	2	Server-side info	1	283.9
11/01/2025 05:27	2	Server-side info	1	1856.5
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11/01/2025 05:28	2	Server-side info	1	270
11/01/2025 05:28	2	Server-side info	1	464.4
11/01/2025 05:29	2	Server-side info	1	301.4

Vanhove Louis

11/01/2025 05:34	2	Server-side info	100	406766
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11/01/2025 05:36	2	Server-side info	100	424887.6
11/01/2025 05:36	2	Server-side info	100	413688.8
11/01/2025 05:37	2	Server-side info	100	403917.1
11/01/2025 05:38	2	Server-side info	100	404128.8
11/01/2025 05:38	2	Server-side info	100	404377.4
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Vanhove Louis

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11/01/2025 05:46	2	Server-side info	10	437087.6
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11/01/2025 05:47	2	Server-side info	10	420911.3
11/01/2025 05:47	2	Server-side info	10	413600.8
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11/01/2025 05:53	2	Server-side info	1000	442907.4
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Vanhove Louis

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11/01/2025 07:19	2	Server-side info	2690	821109.4
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11/01/2025 07:22	2	Server-side info	2690	774689.1
11/01/2025 07:24	2	Server-side info	2690	801005.2
11/01/2025 07:29	2	Server-side info	2690	830500.1
11/01/2025 07:30	2	Server-side info	2690	761685.1
11/01/2025 07:32	2	Server-side info	2690	784033.2
11/01/2025 07:34	2	Server-side info	2690	793721.9

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11/01/2025 07:35	2	Server-side info	2690	794446.6
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11/01/2025 07:47	2	Client-side info	2E+09	2989660
11/01/2025 07:47	2	Client-side info	2E+09	2825715.4
11/01/2025 07:47	2	Client-side info	2E+09	2782371.3
11/01/2025 07:47	2	Client-side info	2E+09	2952136.8
11/01/2025 07:48	2	Client-side info	2E+09	3020726.3
11/01/2025 07:48	2	Client-side info	2E+09	2782647.5
11/01/2025 07:49	2	Client-side info	2E+09	2709482.9
11/01/2025 07:49	2	Client-side info	2E+09	2958688.5

Vanhove Louis

11/01/2025 07:50	2	Client-side info	2E+09	2899131.3
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11/01/2025 07:51	2	Client-side info	2E+09	2792907.9
11/01/2025 07:51	2	Client-side info	2E+09	2870732.3
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11/01/2025 07:53	2	Client-side info	2E+09	2831385.7
11/01/2025 07:53	2	Client-side info	2E+09	2928447.5
11/01/2025 07:53	2	Client-side info	2E+09	2971650.5
11/01/2025 08:44	2	Client-side info	10000000	1532903.8
11/01/2025 08:44	2	Client-side info	10000000	1531419
11/01/2025 08:44	2	Client-side info	10000000	1536482.6
11/01/2025 08:44	2	Client-side info	10000000	1537909.1

Vanhove Louis

11/01/2025 08:44	2	Client-side info	10000000	1522751.4
11/01/2025 08:44	2	Client-side info	10000000	1527923.1
11/01/2025 08:44	2	Client-side info	10000000	1517347.7
11/01/2025 08:45	2	Client-side info	10000000	1524053.7
11/01/2025 08:45	2	Client-side info	10000000	1525517.6
11/01/2025 08:45	2	Client-side info	10000000	1516417.9
11/01/2025 08:45	2	Client-side info	10000000	1519049.5
11/01/2025 08:45	2	Client-side info	10000000	1527238.8
11/01/2025 08:45	2	Client-side info	10000000	1527137
11/01/2025 08:45	2	Client-side info	10000000	1524508.9
11/01/2025 08:45	2	Client-side info	10000000	1510263
11/01/2025 08:45	2	Client-side info	10000000	1534084.1
11/01/2025 08:45	2	Client-side info	10000000	1525650.1

Vanhove Louis

11/01/2025 08:45	2	Client-side info	10000000	1530317.3
11/01/2025 08:51	2	Client-side info	1E+08	1582731.4
11/01/2025 08:51	2	Client-side info	1E+08	1582590.5
11/01/2025 08:51	2	Client-side info	1E+08	1581386.3
11/01/2025 08:51	2	Client-side info	1E+08	1599661.5
11/01/2025 08:51	2	Client-side info	1E+08	1605323.2
11/01/2025 08:51	2	Client-side info	1E+08	1578758.4
11/01/2025 08:51	2	Client-side info	1E+08	1588835.3
11/01/2025 08:51	2	Client-side info	1E+08	1579717.7
11/01/2025 08:51	2	Client-side info	1E+08	1601113.6
11/01/2025 08:51	2	Client-side info	1E+08	1581791.1
11/01/2025 08:52	2	Client-side info	1E+08	1613339.4
11/01/2025 08:52	2	Client-side info	1E+08	1572927.4

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11/01/2025 08:52	2	Client-side info	1E+08	1608305.9
11/01/2025 08:52	2	Client-side info	1E+08	1712361.2
11/01/2025 08:53	2	Client-side info	1E+08	1617065.6
11/01/2025 08:55	2	Client-side info	1E+08	1583749.2
11/01/2025 08:55	2	Client-side info	1E+08	1577604.6
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11/01/2025 08:55	2	Client-side info	1E+08	1588323.8
11/01/2025 08:55	2	Client-side info	1E+08	1579298.7
11/01/2025 08:56	2	Client-side info	1E+08	1614422.8
11/01/2025 08:56	2	Client-side info	1E+08	1587997.9
11/01/2025 08:56	2	Client-side info	1E+08	1581390.6
11/01/2025 08:56	2	Client-side info	1E+08	1582830.2
11/01/2025 08:56	2	Client-side info	1E+08	1610065.9

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11/01/2025 08:56	2	Client-side info	1E+08	1626444.4
11/01/2025 08:56	2	Client-side info	1E+08	1584643.2
11/01/2025 08:56	2	Client-side info	1E+08	1582373.9
11/01/2025 08:57	2	Client-side info	1E+08	1594752.2
11/01/2025 08:57	2	Client-side info	1E+08	1591097.2
11/01/2025 08:57	2	Client-side info	1E+08	1625172.6
11/01/2025 08:57	2	Client-side info	1E+08	1598073.1
11/01/2025 08:57	2	Client-side info	1E+08	1587009.8
11/01/2025 08:57	2	Client-side info	1E+08	1589976.1
11/01/2025 08:58	2	Client-side info	1E+08	1580153.6
11/01/2025 08:58	2	Client-side info	1E+08	1602227
11/01/2025 09:19	2	Client-side info	1	1548036.8
11/01/2025 09:19	2	Client-side info	1	1531331.9

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11/01/2025 09:19	2	Server-side info	2000	642230.5
11/01/2025 09:19	2	Client-side info	1	1522104.2
11/01/2025 09:19	2	Client-side info	1	1530852.1
11/01/2025 09:19	2	Server-side info	2000	608763.3
11/01/2025 09:20	2	Client-side info	1	1593663.3
11/01/2025 09:22	2	Client-side info	1	1520472
11/01/2025 09:23	2	Server-side info	2000	630204
11/01/2025 09:23	2	Client-side info	1	1527175.6
11/01/2025 09:23	2	Client-side info	1	1528008.3
11/01/2025 09:23	2	Server-side info	2000	626228.3
11/01/2025 09:24	2	Client-side info	1	1595921
11/01/2025 09:24	2	Client-side info	1	1536601.9
11/01/2025 09:24	2	Server-side info	2000	645203.4

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11/01/2025 09:24	2	Client-side info	1	1535202.2
11/01/2025 09:25	2	Client-side info	1	1551805.2
11/01/2025 09:25	2	Server-side info	2000	626739
11/01/2025 09:25	2	Client-side info	1	1535966.6
11/01/2025 09:25	2	Client-side info	1	1552241.6
11/01/2025 09:25	2	Server-side info	2000	615117.4
11/01/2025 09:26	2	Client-side info	1	1524956.3
11/01/2025 09:26	2	Client-side info	1	1530111.7
11/01/2025 09:26	2	Server-side info	2000	600116.1
11/01/2025 09:26	2	Client-side info	1	1594295.2
11/01/2025 09:26	2	Client-side info	1	1545467.3
11/01/2025 09:26	2	Server-side info	2000	629714.2
11/01/2025 09:26	2	Client-side info	1	1536372.5

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11/01/2025 09:26	2	Client-side info	1	1525859.9
11/01/2025 09:26	2	Server-side info	2000	600989.6
11/01/2025 09:35	2	Client-side info	1	1546693.1
11/01/2025 09:35	2	Client-side info	1	1546922.2
11/01/2025 09:35	2	Server-side info	500	526193.5
11/01/2025 09:35	2	Client-side info	1	1518117.5
11/01/2025 09:36	2	Client-side info	1	1535183.3
11/01/2025 09:36	2	Server-side info	500	501028.4
11/01/2025 09:36	2	Client-side info	1	1522423.9
11/01/2025 09:36	2	Client-side info	1	1527271.4
11/01/2025 09:36	2	Server-side info	500	516134.6
11/01/2025 09:36	2	Client-side info	1	1584418.7
11/01/2025 09:36	2	Client-side info	1	1538064.6

Vanhove Louis

11/01/2025 09:37	2	Server-side info	500	534704.6
11/01/2025 09:37	2	Client-side info	1	1525718.9
11/01/2025 09:37	2	Client-side info	1	1518796.3
11/01/2025 09:38	2	Server-side info	500	527850.6
11/01/2025 09:38	2	Client-side info	1	1516244.1
11/01/2025 09:38	2	Client-side info	1	1533317.9
11/01/2025 09:38	2	Server-side info	500	505804.7
11/01/2025 09:39	2	Client-side info	1	1526438.1
11/01/2025 09:39	2	Client-side info	1	1576061.6
11/01/2025 09:39	2	Server-side info	500	499463.8
11/01/2025 09:39	2	Client-side info	1	1514964.1
11/01/2025 09:39	2	Client-side info	1	1529748.3
11/01/2025 09:39	2	Server-side info	500	504155.4

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11/01/2025 09:40	2	Client-side info	1	1523900.2
11/01/2025 09:40	2	Client-side info	1	1511251.7
11/01/2025 09:40	2	Server-side info	500	537193.4
11/01/2025 09:40	2	Client-side info	1	1540685.5
11/01/2025 09:40	2	Client-side info	1	1532170.5
11/01/2025 09:41	2	Server-side info	500	549317.7
11/01/2025 09:41	2	Client-side info	1	1524582.1
11/01/2025 09:41	2	Client-side info	1	1554237
11/01/2025 09:41	2	Server-side info	500	520227.5
11/01/2025 09:43	2	Client-side info	1	1538555.8
11/01/2025 09:43	2	Client-side info	1	1526363.9
11/01/2025 09:43	2	Server-side info	500	513595.8
11/01/2025 09:45	2	Client-side info	100000	1546227.1

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11/01/2025 09:45	2	Client-side info	100000	1508274.8
11/01/2025 09:45	2	Client-side info	100000	1515768
11/01/2025 09:45	2	Client-side info	100000	1520847.6
11/01/2025 09:45	2	Client-side info	100000	1535310.1
11/01/2025 09:45	2	Client-side info	100000	1506083.4
11/01/2025 09:45	2	Client-side info	100000	1512819.5
11/01/2025 09:46	2	Client-side info	100000	1521638.1
11/01/2025 09:46	2	Client-side info	100000	1537983.9
11/01/2025 09:46	2	Client-side info	100000	1508751.4
11/01/2025 09:46	2	Client-side info	100000	1513859.5
11/01/2025 09:46	2	Client-side info	100000	1518255
11/01/2025 09:46	2	Client-side info	100000	1529264.8
11/01/2025 09:46	2	Client-side info	100000	1529578.4

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11/01/2025 09:46	2	Client-side info	100000	1514690
11/01/2025 09:46	2	Client-side info	100000	1531111
11/01/2025 09:46	2	Client-side info	100000	1525102.2
11/01/2025 09:46	2	Client-side info	100000	1517334.5
11/01/2025 09:46	2	Client-side info	100000	1512500.4
11/01/2025 09:47	2	Client-side info	100000	1549622.8
11/01/2025 09:47	2	Client-side info	100000	1521211.5
11/01/2025 09:47	2	Client-side info	100000	1529680.8
11/01/2025 09:47	2	Client-side info	100000	1523411.3
11/01/2025 09:47	2	Client-side info	100000	1531321.7
11/01/2025 09:47	2	Client-side info	100000	1528818
11/01/2025 09:47	2	Client-side info	100000	1516813.2
11/01/2025 09:47	2	Client-side info	100000	1507511.6

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11/01/2025 09:47	2	Client-side info	100000	1531524.5
11/01/2025 09:47	2	Client-side info	100000	1527359.1
11/01/2025 09:47	2	Client-side info	100000	1524432.1
11/01/2025 09:47	2	Client-side info	100000	1549622.5
11/01/2025 09:48	2	Client-side info	100000	1552740.1
11/01/2025 09:48	2	Client-side info	100000	1522726.5
11/01/2025 09:48	2	Client-side info	100000	1519893.9
12/01/2025 04:41	2	Client-side info	5E+08	1786799.6
12/01/2025 04:41	2	Client-side info	5E+08	1728832
12/01/2025 04:41	2	Client-side info	5E+08	1691736.3
12/01/2025 04:41	2	Client-side info	5E+08	1766503.4
12/01/2025 04:41	2	Client-side info	5E+08	1765412
12/01/2025 04:41	2	Client-side info	5E+08	1717902.5

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12/01/2025 04:41	2	Client-side info	5E+08	1698994
12/01/2025 04:41	2	Client-side info	5E+08	1759026.8
12/01/2025 04:41	2	Client-side info	5E+08	1830473.3
12/01/2025 04:41	2	Client-side info	5E+08	1785990
12/01/2025 04:42	2	Client-side info	5E+08	1758876.3
12/01/2025 04:42	2	Client-side info	5E+08	1772301.1
12/01/2025 04:42	2	Client-side info	5E+08	1746009.2
12/01/2025 04:42	2	Client-side info	5E+08	1730996.1
12/01/2025 04:42	2	Client-side info	5E+08	1699473.5
12/01/2025 04:42	2	Client-side info	5E+08	1748920.8
12/01/2025 04:42	2	Client-side info	5E+08	1753526.4
12/01/2025 04:42	2	Client-side info	5E+08	1747833.8
12/01/2025 04:42	2	Client-side info	5E+08	1696822.5

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12/01/2025 04:42	2	Client-side info	5E+08	1757502.5
12/01/2025 04:43	2	Client-side info	5E+08	1754345.7
12/01/2025 04:43	2	Client-side info	5E+08	1711050.6
12/01/2025 04:45	2	Client-side info	1.5E+09	2396840
12/01/2025 04:45	2	Client-side info	1.5E+09	2436950.1
12/01/2025 04:45	2	Client-side info	1.5E+09	2634168.1
12/01/2025 04:45	2	Client-side info	1.5E+09	2425358.9
12/01/2025 04:46	2	Client-side info	1.5E+09	2423513.9
12/01/2025 04:46	2	Client-side info	1.5E+09	2470833.2
12/01/2025 04:46	2	Client-side info	1.5E+09	2431887
12/01/2025 04:46	2	Client-side info	1.5E+09	2385053
12/01/2025 04:47	2	Client-side info	1.5E+09	2368217.5
12/01/2025 04:47	2	Client-side info	1.5E+09	2443939.1

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12/01/2025 04:47	2	Client-side info	1.5E+09	2415891.7
12/01/2025 04:47	2	Client-side info	1.5E+09	2360083.1
12/01/2025 04:47	2	Client-side info	1.5E+09	2345442.5
12/01/2025 04:49	2	Client-side info	1.5E+09	2383405.9
12/01/2025 04:49	2	Client-side info	1.5E+09	2345564.6
12/01/2025 04:49	2	Client-side info	1.5E+09	2332506.8
12/01/2025 04:49	2	Client-side info	1.5E+09	2359442.3
12/01/2025 04:50	2	Client-side info	1.5E+09	2347597.6
12/01/2025 04:50	2	Client-side info	1.5E+09	2341753.7
12/01/2025 04:50	2	Client-side info	1.5E+09	2357615.4
12/01/2025 04:52	2	Client-side info	1.5E+09	2355896.7
12/01/2025 04:52	2	Client-side info	1.5E+09	2372443.2
12/01/2025 04:52	2	Client-side info	1.5E+09	2406567

12/01/2025 04:52 2 Client-side info 1.5E+09 2396112.7

This data is retrieved through the BenchmarkManager.cs script you can find in Appendix 1.

APPENDIX 4: R CODE FOR DATA ANALYSIS

R script for the statistical data analysis:

```
library("tidyverse")

library("scales")

library("dplyr")

results <- read_csv("BenchmarkResults.csv")

#for the client

client <- results %>%

filter(Sync_Method == "Client-side info")

plot_1 <- ggplot(data = client, aes(x = Extra_Packets, y = log(Duration_Microseconds))) +

geom_point(alpha = 0.5) +

stat_smooth(method = "lm", se = TRUE, color = "blue") +

labs(

title = "Client-side Info Sync Method log(Duration)",

x = "Extra Bytes/Packets",

y = "Log(Duration in Microseconds)"

)

#for the client with the base 10 transformed duration

client_trans <- client %>%

mutate(Log10_Duration = log10(Duration_Microseconds))

plot_2 <- ggplot(data = client_trans, aes(x = Extra_Packets, y=Log10_Duration)) +

geom_point(alpha = 0.5) +

stat_smooth(method = "lm", se = TRUE, color = "red")+

labs(
```

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```
title = "Client-side Info Synch Method log10(Duration)",
x = "Extra Bytes/Packets",
y = "Log10(Duration in microseconds)"
)
##### Main one for client
client_trans <- client %>%
mutate(
  Log10_Duration = log10(Duration_Microseconds),
  Log10_Extra_Packets = log10(Extra_Packets)
)
plot_3 <- ggplot(data = client_trans, aes(x = Log10_Extra_Packets, y = Log10_Duration)) +
  geom_point(alpha = 0.5) +
  stat_smooth(method = "lm", se = TRUE, color = "red") +
  scale_x_continuous(
    breaks = seq(floor(min(client_trans$Log10_Extra_Packets, na.rm = TRUE)),
ceiling(max(client_trans$Log10_Extra_Packets, na.rm = TRUE)), by = 1),
    labels = math_format(10^.x)
  ) +
  scale_y_continuous(
    limits = c(6, 8),
    breaks = seq(6, 8, by = 1),
    labels = math_format(10^.x),
    expand = expansion(mult = c(0, 0))
  ) +
  coord_cartesian(clip = "off") +
  labs(
    title = "Syncing Client-side Info",
    x = expression(10^n ~ "Extra Bytes/Packets"),
    y = expression(10^n ~ "Duration in Microseconds")
  )
```

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```
)  
  
#for the client non-logged:  
  
plot_4 <- ggplot(data = client, aes(x = Extra_Packets, y = Duration_Microseconds)) +  
  geom_point(alpha = 0.5) +  
  stat_smooth(method = "lm", se = TRUE, color = "blue") +  
  labs(  
    title = "Syncing Client-side Info (raw data)",  
    x = "Extra Bytes/Packets",  
    y = "Duration in Microseconds"  
  )  
  
#Linear Regression Model Fitting for client with log(Duration)  
  
#client_model <- lm(log(Duration_Microseconds) ~ Extra_Packets, data = client)  
  
#summary(client_model)  
  
#Linear Regression Model Fitting for client with log10(Duration)  
  
#client_model_transformed <- lm(Log10_Duration ~ Extra_Packets, data = client_trans)  
  
#summary(client_model_transformed)  
  
#####  
  
#for the server  
  
server <- results %>%  
  filter(Sync_Method == "Server-side info")  
  
plot_5 <- ggplot(data=server, aes(x=Extra_Packets, y=log(Duration_Microseconds))) +  
  geom_point(alpha = 0.5) +  
  stat_smooth(method = "lm", se = TRUE, color = "blue") +  
  labs(  
    title = "Server-side info Sync Method log(Duration)",  
    x="Extra bytes/packets",  
    y="log(Duration in Microseconds)"  
  )  
  
#for the server with the base 10 transformed duration
```

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```
server_trans <- server %>%

mutate(Log10_Duration = log10(Duration_Microseconds))

plot_6 <- ggplot(data = server_trans, aes(x = Extra_Packets, y=Log10_Duration)) +

geom_point(alpha = 0.5) +

stat_smooth(method = "lm", se = TRUE, color = "red")+

labs(

title = "Server-side Info Synch Method log10(Duration)",

x = "Extra Bytes/Packets",

y = "Log10(Duration in microseconds)"

)

##### Main one for server

server_trans <- server %>%

mutate(

Log10_Duration = log10(Duration_Microseconds),

Log10_Extra_Packets = log10(Extra_Packets)

)

plot_7 <- ggplot(data = server_trans, aes(x = Log10_Extra_Packets, y = Log10_Duration)) +

geom_point(alpha = 0.5) +

stat_smooth(method = "lm", se = TRUE, color = "red") +

scale_x_continuous(

breaks = seq(floor(min(server_trans$Log10_Extra_Packets)),

ceiling(max(server_trans$Log10_Extra_Packets)), by = 1),

labels = math_format(10^.x)

) +

scale_y_continuous(

breaks = seq(floor(min(server_trans$Log10_Duration)),

ceiling(max(server_trans$Log10_Duration)), by = 1),

labels = math_format(10^.x)

) +
```

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```
labs(  
  
title = "Syncing Server-side Info",  
  
x = expression(10^n ~ "Extra Bytes/Packets"),  
  
y = expression(10^n ~ "Duration in Microseconds")  
  
) +  
  
theme_minimal()  
  
#for the server non-logged:  
  
plot_8 <- ggplot(data=server, aes(x=Extra_Packets, y=Duration_Microseconds)) +  
geom_point(alpha = 0.5) +  
stat_smooth(method = "lm", se = TRUE, color = "blue") +  
  
labs(  
  
title = "Syncing Server-side Info (raw data)",  
  
x="Extra bytes/packets",  
  
y="Duration in Microseconds"  
  
)  
  
#Linear Regression Model Fitting for server with log(Duration)  
  
#server_model <- lm(log(Duration_Microseconds) ~ Extra_Packets, data = server)  
  
#summary(server_model)  
  
#Linear Regression Model Fitting for server with log10(Duration)  
  
#server_model_transformed <- lm(Log10_Duration ~ Extra_Packets, data = server_trans)  
  
#summary(server_model_transformed)  
  
#To save all of the plots  
  
plot_list <- list(plot_1 = plot_1, plot_2 = plot_2, plot_3 = plot_3, plot_4 = plot_4,  
plot_5 = plot_5, plot_6 = plot_6, plot_7 = plot_7, plot_8 = plot_8)  
  
pdf("All_Plots.pdf", width = 8, height = 6)  
  
for (p in plot_list) {  
  
print(p)  
  
}d  
  
ev.off()
```

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```
##### Final Linear Regression Models on Base 10

# Linear regression on log-transformed data - client

model_log_log_client <- lm(Log10_Duration ~ Log10_Extra_Packets, data = client_trans)

summary(model_log_log_client)

coefficients_c <- coef(model_log_log_client)

intercept_c <- coefficients_c[1]

slope_c <- coef(model_log_log_client)["Log10_Extra_Packets"]

residuals_c <- residuals(model_log_log_client)

client_reg_form <- paste0("Log10_Duration = ", round(intercept_c, 8), " + ", round(slope_c,
8), " * Log10_Extra_Packets + e")

client_reg_form

# Linear regression on log-transformed data - server

model_log_log_server <- lm(Log10_Duration ~ Log10_Extra_Packets, data = server_trans)

summary(model_log_log_server)

coefficients_s <- coef(model_log_log_server)

intercept_s <- coefficients_s[1]

slope_s <- coef(model_log_log_server)["Log10_Extra_Packets"]

residuals_s <- residuals(model_log_log_server)

server_reg_form <- paste0("Log10_Duration = ", round(intercept_s, 8), " + ", round(slope_s,
8), " * Log10_Extra_Packets + e")

server_reg_form
```